

IRRI 1996-1997

Partners

Making a Difference

IRRI
INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE

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Research partners make the difference

The challenge of maintaining food security is so immense that no one organization can produce the new technologies required.

The essence of rice research is about discovery—and about sharing that knowledge with others to make a difference in the lives of ordinary people.

The world's first researchers were farmers. They realized the importance of asking why, of experimenting, of sharing information, and of working together. That farmers successfully domesticated the rice plant thousands of years before any formal scientific institutions existed is a testimonial to their remarkable research abilities.

Although much of this indigenous knowledge has been handed down through the millennia, farmers have also been extremely responsive to change resulting from the advent of modern science and technology. Many of these striking successes can be attributed to the partnerships forged among farmers, extension workers, and scientists. In recent years, the trend toward partnerships in research has only intensified.

This year's Corporate Report focuses on these research alliances—especially those between IRRI scientists and their counterparts in national agricultural research systems (NARS) in developing and developed countries—and how they are making a difference in the lives of the world's rice farmers and consumers. The importance of linkages among public-sector scientists in advanced laboratories, private sector entrepreneurs, workers from nongovernment organizations (NGOs), and farmers are also highlighted.

The challenge of maintaining food security as the world's population doubles during the next 40 years—and the availability of water and suitable land for agriculture decreases—is so immense that no one organization can produce the new technologies required. IRRI represents only 4 percent of all the research efforts targeted at producing these technologies.

These partnerships take many forms and are especially important in the rainfed rice environments, where extremely unpredictable climatic conditions, such as drought and flooding, often prevail. The Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium is a good model. The dedicated efforts of multidisciplinary teams of NARS and IRRI scientists—together with extension workers—at key sites in five Asian countries are having significant impact in improving the lives of rice farmers.

The harsh, variable environments in which deepwater rice is produced require a similar research approach. Using Thailand as the “hub,” IRRI acts as a coordinator for partners in Bangladesh, Cambodia, India, and Myanmar. Thailand, with its extensive knowledge of and experience in deepwater rice research, has its own work well in hand. The nation's researchers see their role as one of helping build the capacities of less experienced partner countries.

IRRI has had several major projects addressing the need for building capacity in less advanced national systems. Its work in Madagascar has been particularly successful. The example featured highlights the partnerships that have been cultivated among Malagasy and IRRI scientists, a United Nations volunteer, NGO workers, farmers, and private sector entrepreneurs in an all-out effort to make appropriate animal-drawn machinery available to farmers.

Even in the more favorable areas that produce cereals for more than 350 million people, the major problems in maintaining yields can only be addressed through effective and wide-ranging partnerships. The Rice-Wheat Consortium for the Indo-Gangetic Plains illustrates the benefits of having partnerships that are “national system-driven,” and where IRRI and other international agricultural research centers provide strategic technical support and training. The second example from the irrigated production

system focuses on hybrid rice in India. Already well on the way to being developed, this technology requires a very particular kind of partnership to meet the awesome target of planting 2 million hectares to hybrid rice by 2000. This effort embraces the national system through the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, the private sector, foundations, NGOs, farmers, and IRRI.

The remaining features emphasize the all-important human elements in partnerships. The Shuttle Program with Japan provides immensely valuable scientific exchanges and training for Japanese and IRRI counterparts—at both the senior scientist and graduate student levels—as well as creating important opportunities for increasing appreciation for other cultures.

The secondment to IRRI of French scientists from the Annual Crops Department of the Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD-CA) and the Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopéra-

tion (ORSTOM) as a significant component of France's contribution to the Institute has been of immeasurable value. The alliance has provided continuity to several major long-term programs that would otherwise have been impossible.

This leads me to a final acknowledgment of a group of crucially important partners in every venture that IRRI and its counterparts are involved in: our key donors. Through their dedicated efforts, often in the face of their own governments' lack of enthusiasm for supporting development assistance—particularly international agricultural research—they continue to provide us with the funding that makes all these efforts possible. Without our donors, IRRI and its partners wouldn't be able to make the difference.

George Rothschild
Director General

Diverse partners working toward a common goal is the essence of rice research.

Partners make hybrid rice a reality in India

I had my doubts about the eating quality of hybrid rice," says Karnataka farmer K.B. Boregowda. "So at first I sold most of it. Then I discovered my family likes the taste, so now we eat all the hybrid rice we grow."

If all goes according to plan, thousands of Indian farmers like Mr. Boregowda will be growing hybrid rice on 2 million hectares by 2000. Only a few years ago, many would have thought this a dream. But not today.

Indian agricultural planners are confident that this goal is realistic, thanks to the determination and cooperation of diverse partners in national and international public research institutions, private foundations and seed companies, and nongovernment organizations (NGOs) in collaboration with farmers. And hybrid rice is getting into Indian fields not a moment too soon.

"Population growth and the gradually increasing purchasing power of consumers mean that India must increase its rough rice production by 3 percent annually," says Dr. R.S. Paroda, director general of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR).

This means that by 2010, India will need 195 million tons of rice each year, and by 2020, the demand will be a staggering 240 million tons.

How will this additional rice be produced?

India already dedicates more of its precious land to rice than any other country: 42 million hectares. Planting more land to rice is definitely out of the question because there simply isn't any unused land left. The solution must come from squeezing more grains from each plant—and hybrid rice does this.

Farmers eagerly await hybrid rice seed being produced at the Regional Research Station of the University of Agricultural Sciences in Mandya, Karnataka, India.

Hybrid rice's steady evolution

Indian agricultural researchers and farmers have a track record of successfully scaling formidable challenges. Their stunning accomplishments in both rice and wheat during the Green Revolution in the 1960s and 1970s saved millions from famine. Now, as then, many players are involved.

Eighteen years ago, scientists from ICAR and IRRI had the foresight to start the painstaking process of developing hybrid rice technology.

Hybrids take advantage of a phenomenon called heterosis—or hybrid vigor—which enables the offspring of two genetically diverse plants to produce more grain than either parent. Taking advantage of hybrid vigor in plants has been one of the most important applications of genetics in agriculture.

Scientists from ICAR closely observed China's accomplishments with hybrid rice in subtropical and temperate environments as well as IRRI's expanding tropical hybrid rice effort. In 1989, ICAR, with support from the United Nations Development Programme, launched a national hybrid rice project resulting in 12 strategically located hybrid rice research centers (see map).

Through this effort, India has released seven rice hybrids through public institutions or private seed companies.

"The hybrids emanating from the India-IRRI collaboration are typically producing 15-20 percent—or 1 ton per hectare—more than the improved semidwarf, inbred varieties that farmers are growing today," says Dr. Sant S. Virmani, IRRI's hybrid rice breeder.

In 1996, Indian farmers planted 50,000 hectares to these hybrids.

India has embarked on an ambitious quest to motivate farmers to grow 2 million hectares of hybrid rice by 2000.

Dr. Sant Virmani
directs IRRI's hybrid
rice effort.

K. Hamdorf

Ambitious efforts are now under way to motivate them to grow an additional 1,950,000 hectares of hybrid rice by 2000.

IRRI's critical role

Toward making this challenging goal a reality, IRRI has played a key role in helping to establish a strong and sustainable research program on hybrid rice in India.

In this effort, the Institute has emphasized developing human resources, supplying hybrid rice breeding materials adapted to tropical conditions, and providing consultancy services. To date, 46 Indian scientists have been trained in hybrid rice-related areas through degree and non-degree programs. The Institute has also developed an illustrated *Manual for hybrid rice seed production* (already in its second printing), slide tapes, and a video to enhance the training effort.

Over the life of the collaboration, IRRI has supplied to Indian scientists 84 genetically diverse cytoplasmic male sterile lines (female parents) and 232 experimental rice hybrids and their respective restorer lines (male parents).

"These materials are showing up in most of the first hybrids being released in India by both the public and private sectors," Dr. Virmani says.

Public and private sectors team up

A strong partnership between the public and private sectors is another element fueling the effort. E.I.D. Parry Ltd., a highly diversified Tamil Nadu-based company, provides a good example. It made its first foray into hybrid rice 4 years ago.

To get farmers interested in growing hybrid rice, Parry has been promoting CORH 1 (MGR)—a hybrid developed by Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU) in collaboration with IRRI. The hybrid, released by TNAU in 1994, is gaining popularity in the state through both the private and public sectors.

The head of the TNAU breeding team in Coimbatore that selected COHR 1, Dr. M. Rangaswamy, is a proponent of this public-private sector marriage as a way to more quickly commercialize public hybrids. "Private companies are more willing to take risks," he points out. "And they are not governed by the cumbersome state seed certification laws that the public sector must follow."

Veteran public-sector rice breeder goes private

When should a public researcher consider turning private? After more than 20 years as a rice breeder in the public sector, Dr. Ish Kumar realized that he could probably better serve farmers from the private sector. So he joined ProAgro Seed Company Limited as its research coordinator and shortly thereafter formed Hybrid Rice International Ltd (HRI) in Hyderabad as a subsidiary company devoted solely to hybrid rice.

"I am serving the same farmers I would have served if I had remained at the Punjab Agricultural University," Dr. Kumar emphasizes.

Although the public sector has important advantages in conducting basic research, doing testing and field demonstrations, educating researchers, and developing germplasm, Dr. Kumar believes the private sector has the distinctive advantage of being able to get large amounts of quality hybrid seed to farmers rapidly. And this is precisely the critical next step in India if hybrid rice is to become a successful crop.

Dr. Kumar is optimistic about the future of HRI, which has already made a dent in the market. "I expect my company to sell hybrid rice seed for nearly 81,000 hectares in 1997 in various states of India, particularly in the east where our hybrid variety, 6201, is showing a yield superiority of nearly 25 percent over conventional varieties," says the breeder.

G. Hettel

In addition to promoting public hybrids, Parry is also developing its own hybrids—using germplasm from the China National Rice Research Institute and from IRRI.

“We have been getting excellent assistance in acquiring appropriate germplasm from institutions such as IRRI,” says Dr. M.C. Gopinathan, Parry’s deputy general manager for research and development.

Dr. Gopinathan stresses that he wants to continue cultivating Parry’s cordial association with the public sector to bring Indian farmers into the forefront of hybrid rice technology.

Breaking down barriers

Although a lot of progress has been made, some people, including Dr. B. Vidya Chandra, a hybrid rice breeder at the University of Agricultural Sciences in Mandya, Karnataka, look cautiously at the public-private sector union.

Dr. Vidya Chandra, who recently visited Parry’s breeding and tissue culture center in Bangalore, feels that private companies also should be provided with public germplasm for developing their own hybrids. “But,” he says, “the transaction should be well recorded and the private company should give credit to those who developed the material.”

Many other questions remain unanswered. One of the most burning issues is whether private companies will be allowed to have exclusive rights to market some publicly developed hybrids. Parry’s Dr. Gopinathan speculates that the delicate balance between public and private sectors will depend on long-term government strategy and policy—and companies’ own policies.

Farmer cashing in on hybrid rice

Farmer K.B. Boregowda is all smiles these days as he displays the photocopy of a 25,000-rupee check (US\$715) he won in a local rice yield contest—using hybrid variety KRH-1.

And if Mr. Boregowda is happy, then euphoric must be the emotion that describes both IRRI’s Dr. Sant S. Virmani, and Karnataka State’s Dr. B. Vidya Chandra. Dr. Virmani bred this hybrid (IR64611H) at IRRI and Dr. Vidya Chandra introduced, evaluated, and released the hybrid as KRH-1 at the Regional Research Station of the University of Agricultural Sciences at Mandya.

“I can think of no better way for farmers to take notice of the new hybrid technology,” says Dr. Vidya Chandra. “Winning the contest was a great advertisement for KRH-1 to handily beat its competition—all inbred varieties of 34 other farmers.”

KRH-1 is the first hybrid rice released by the University, although breeders there have several other hybrids in the pipeline.

Mr. Boregowda won the Karnataka State-sponsored contest with an official yield of 39 quintals per acre (9.6 tons per hectare). The closest competition yielded only 28 quintals per acre (6.9 tons per hectare).

“I am sorry that I did not enter my name at the district level because I was told that I would have won that competition as well,” says Mr. Boregowda, who put his prize money in the bank for future investments on his 4-hectare farm in Kuduragundi Village, Mandya District.

Even if he had not won first prize, the farmer would still have good things to say about hybrid rice. In addition to the better yields—his inbreds usually produce around 5 to 6 tons per hectare—he is pleasantly surprised by the taste.

The farmer is already excited about competing again. “Next year, I’ll skip the local and district levels and just compete at the state level,” he says confidently.

Dr. Vidya Chandra, however, tries to put in a few words of caution: “It may not be so easy to win next year as news of the higher yielding rices spreads and other farmers begin adopting them.”

Dr. B. Vidya Chandra (left) and Mr. K.B. Boregowda plan to capture another rice yield championship next year.

G. Hettel

Private companies contributing

Currently, 15 private seed companies across India, such as Parry and Hybrid Rice International Ltd (see sidebar, p 6), are investing seriously in hybrid rice.

Both ICAR and IRRI staff recognized years ago that private firms have crucial roles in getting hybrid rice technology to farmers. IRRI has established a protocol for sharing its hybrid rice parental lines with both the private and public sectors.

“We have supplied germplasm not only to Parry and Hybrid Rice International but to seven other Indian seed companies as well,” says Dr. Virmani.

ICAR also saw the light. “We involved the private sector in testing and transferring hybrid rice technology as soon as we identified some promising parental lines and hybrids,” adds Dr. E.A. Siddiq, ICAR deputy director general.

Whether hybrids are privately or publicly developed, farmers—and consumers—are the ultimate beneficiaries. “The true measure of the success of hybrid rice will be farmer acceptance,” says Dr. Virmani.

An excellent example is Mr. K.B. Boregowda, the farmer mentioned earlier. See the sidebar (p 7) for why taste is not the only reason he and his family are pleased with their hybrid rice.

Foundations and NGOs join effort

Encouraged by the potential of hybrid rice in India, private foundations and NGOs are also becoming actively involved.

The Madras-based M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation has come up with one of the most novel and exciting of the endeavors: the seed village.

“We get parent seeds from Indo-American Hybrid Seeds in Bangalore,” explains Dr. Swaminathan, “and teach the very poor local women—and men—to make the crosses. We then arrange a buy-back. Everyone wins: the companies get good quality seed, and previously unskilled people have vastly improved livelihoods.”

Villages are currently producing hybrid seed for tomato and sunflower. Dr. Swaminathan is confident that rice hybrids will be next. The Foundation is also conducting on-farm comparative studies of public and private rice hybrids. Once the results are in, Dr. Swaminathan predicts that hybrid rice will “catch on like wildfire.”

G. Heitel

In Mumbai, the MAHYCO Research Foundation recently translated IRRI's *Manual for hybrid rice seed production* into six Indian languages (Hindi, Kannada, Punjabi, Telegu, Marathi, and Tamil) as part of an effort to train farmers to become hybrid rice seed growers more quickly.

Nongovernment organizations are joining the movement, too. In Andhra Pradesh, the Sri Aurobindo Institute of Rural Development is producing—through the hundreds of farmers it has trained—foundation and certified seeds of publicly developed parental lines and hybrids. It then provides the hybrid seed to other farmers to grow in their fields.

“If properly trained, farmers can become entrepreneurs by selling hybrid rice seed directly to other farmers,” says Dr. G. Gopal Reddy, the NGO’s founder. By doing this, hybrid seed costs can be reduced.

“India has a need for intermediate agencies between public breeders and the private sector, not only for rice but for other hybrid crops as well,” says MAHYCO board member Dr. Wayne H. Freeman. He sees this to be an ideal role for NGOs such as Dr. Reddy’s.

“In serving as intermediaries,” Dr. Freeman adds, “Sri Aurobindo and others must implement procedures that will assure genetic purity of the hybrids released to farmers.”

No longer a dream

If the target of 2 million hectares of hybrid rice in farmers’ fields is reached by 2000, it will increase India’s annual production of rough rice by 2 million tons, worth at least US\$200 million. With so many players actively and enthusiastically involved, it seems likely that the country can attain its target.

MAHYCO’s Dr. Freeman agrees: “Someone once said, ‘Make no small plans for they have not the magic to stir the minds of men.’ When the hybrid rice target is reached, the stage will be set to achieve still greater targets helping more farmers grow more rice, and allowing more people to eat more rice as their daily staple food.” ■

IRRI hybrid breeding team members, Mr. Rody Toledo (left) and Mr. Carlos Casal (center), and E.I.D. Parry breeder Dr. A.V. Kini inspect the performance of an IRRI-produced hybrid at Parry’s Bangalore research station.

Forging partnerships in Madagascar

A budding agricultural machinery program encourages innovative partnerships among diverse organizations.

“Gauche (left!)” commands the Malagasy farmer to the cattle, his whip slicing through the dragonfly-filled early morning air.

The animals, however, have minds of their own, and they charge to the right, dragging the plow—and farmer—with them.

“Aoka (stop)!” he shouts. They obey, taking a break from preparing land for upland rice.

In rural Madagascar, animals—and humans—continue to supply much of the power for agriculture, most of which revolves around rice, the preferred staple food. But the country cannot

produce enough of the grain to meet its own needs—so it must import.

“Unless sustainable improvements are made in rice productivity, broader growth of the Malagasy economy cannot be expected,” warns Dr. Martha Gaudreau, agronomist and team leader for the Madagascar-IRRI Rice Research Project, which began in 1984 with funding from the United States Agency for International Development.

“Agricultural mechanization is the key to improving the labor productivity of farmers, reducing drudgery, and boosting the economy,” advocates the scientist.

Maneuvering blockages

During the 1980s, tractors and other motorized machines simply became too expensive for farmers compared with draft power. As a result, rural development organizations and the extension system started to promote animal traction. The Madagascar-IRRI Project and the National Center for Applied Research and Rural Development (FOFIFA) soon followed their lead, and began testing, adapting, and promoting animal-drawn machinery.

“Although farmers really liked the motorized equipment, none had been adopted after 10 years of work,” Dr. Gaudreau explains. “So we asked ourselves why? Where were the blockages?”

The answer soon became clear: no private-sector companies were manufacturing the machinery, and even if farmers could have bought something, no affordable credit was available.

“So we decided to tackle the problems limiting adoption and use of new agricultural machinery: cost and availability, credit, and training,” says Dr. Gaudreau. Some of these elements, however, were beyond the mandates of IRRI and FOFIFA. So the private sector was looked to for

manufacturing and nongovernment organizations (NGOs) for providing credit.

“We all have the same objective of rural development, so shouldn’t we work together anyway?” she asks.

Credit helps farmers grow

To start working on the credit front, the Madagascar-IRRI Project linked up with one of the most successful NGOs in Madagascar: Formation pour l’Epanouissement et le renouveau de la terre (FERT). This French-based organization has been working in Madagascar for 10 years, providing credit, running stores, and organizing 150 farmer groups in Mahajanga Province—and 1,500 nationwide.

“Working as partners is important because IRRI does not do the work FERT does, and FERT does not do the work IRRI does,” says Mr. Marc Bergeron, FERT regional coordinator.

The Caisse d’Epargne et de Crédit Agricole Mutuels (CECAM) in Tsaratanàna is one of eight rural banks in the area organized by FERT. Eighty-six members belong to CECAM, with each annually paying 20,000 Malagasy francs (US\$4.75) in membership fees.

Through small loans and lease-sale access to equipment, farmers can purchase agricultural machinery on reasonable terms—rather than at the usurious rates often charged by commercial stores. In the lease-sale system, farmers make regular rental payments toward purchasing a piece of equipment; a portion goes to CECAM.

Farmers may also borrow money for crop inputs through the savings association, which pays its depositors 2 percent interest on their money; a cement box with a lock serves as a safe. An eight-member managing committee from the village decides who will receive loans. During its first year, the organization had 44 loan requests, totaling 5.6 million Malagasy francs (US\$1,320), but not all were approved.

“The system is working very well. We’ve had 100 percent recovery of the loans so far,” says Mr. Bergeron, noting that the smallest loan was 100,000 Malagasy francs (US\$24).

J. Lazaro/M. Wenceslao

C. Dedolph

Seeing is believing: demonstrating agricultural machinery to farmers gets their attention and they pass the word to others.

Stores ideal for sharing information

The eight FERT stores have become important community fixtures. The one in Befandriana, for example, sells everything from vegetable and rice seeds to veterinary supplies to plows. Raw materials for blacksmiths will also soon be available. FERT follows the cooperative philosophy of buying materials in bulk and then passing on the savings to its patrons, with the retail prices being much less than those in commercial enterprises.

The stores have become a natural place for organizing farmers and for sharing information with them. The Befandriana storekeeper—who is also a farmer—estimates that about 20 customers come in each day. He laments that the eight stores' main problem is getting the local foundry to fill machinery orders within a reasonable time.

Seeing is believing

In April 1995, the Madagascar-IRRI Project hired an agricultural machinery specialist and United Nations volunteer, Mr. Pamphile Sinha, whose first task was to determine the equipment needs of the rural people. He started by talking with

farmers and blacksmiths; holding meetings with NGOs, extension, and foundry workers; and studying the results of recent surveys. He learned that few farmers have much equipment.

Under the specialist's guidance, four prototype machines were identified, tested, modified according to farmer feedback, and then demonstrated to farmers' groups. As a part of these efforts, FOFIFA and IRRI initiated training activities with the extension service, farmers' associations, and development agencies to teach about proper use and maintenance of the equipment.

Mr. Sinha and his FOFIFA colleagues have demonstrated the conopuddler (a machine for turning flooded, plowed land into mud), a simple pump, and a plow with accessories for weeding, harvesting peanuts, and digging furrows, and several other items. Ever concerned about farmers' needs, the specialist emphasizes that he never demonstrates any equipment without knowing farmers' problems—from their viewpoint.

"Farmers are willing to buy the equipment because they've seen how it works through demonstrations," says Mr. Sinha, who has also been training his FOFIFA counterparts.

The first farmer in the Marotandrano area to have bought a conopuddler is Mr. Ravelomasina.

"Before they were stolen, I used 20 cattle to trample my land to prepare it for planting rice. Now I own one pair and a conopuddler. It's much safer and I make more money," he says.

Mr. Ravelomasina purchased the machine through FERT's lease-sell scheme for 1.5 million Malagasy francs (US\$357). He paid 25 percent down and will pay off the balance over 3 years. He says he can now prepare his land much more quickly with the conopuddler—and then he rents it out.

Animal traction school a success

Another endeavor has been for FOFIFA, with support from IRRI, to establish a center for selecting and training draft animals at the Miadana Agricultural Station near Mahajanga. Participants include extension and NGO technicians and selected farmers, who will someday conduct training sessions of their own.

"We train people in these schools, not animals," Mr. Sinha says, explaining that animal traction training centers used to be common, but they were all closed long ago.

Blacksmiths produce most of the agricultural machinery in Madagascar.

R. Cabrera

Struggling foundry retools operations

The Suppliers of Equipment for Industry and Crop Production (FIF) is a private foundry located on the outskirts of Mahajanga. Founded in 1972, it is the only producer of agricultural machinery in northern Madagascar.

Teetering on the verge of bankruptcy, FIF's production has receded to a trickle. And because of poor raw materials, the machinery it does produce has been of inferior quality—tarnishing its reputation among farmers. IRRI and FOFIFA have been working with FIF to help it once again make good quality, reliable agricultural machinery that farmers need.

Thanks to its interactions with IRRI, FIF's manager, Mr. Mounawar, says the foundry is now using blueprints to manufacture its machines—something the company had never done before.

FIF recently hired a new technical adviser to renew and modernize the foundry, which makes use of 1920–vintage technology. FIF is also diversifying its machinery line to include conopuddlers, plows and accessories, peanut harvesters, and drum seeders.

“If the foundry can target production to meet demand and manufacture machinery using an assembly line, the potential is there for FIF to become profitable again,” projects Dr. Gaudreau.

Blacksmiths forging the way

A natural division exists in fabricating agricultural machinery: big foundries make the complicated equipment (such as the conopuddler), and small blacksmiths make simple equipment (such as weeders and spades)—and repair the more complicated machines.

Whether large or small, the main obstacle confronting these entrepreneurs has been getting decent quality raw materials—steel, iron, sheet metal, angle irons, and pipes—at affordable prices.

Although no formal blacksmith groups previously existed, FERT helped establish two groups in Mandritsara and Befandriana. IRRI and FOFIFA held two training sessions to assess skill levels, visit forges, and teach the participants about new machinery and how to make repairs.

To help the blacksmiths, FERT will soon be selling raw materials through its stores and providing credit to them. The machinery they fabricate will then be sold through the stores.

R. Cabrera

R. Cabrera

Mobilizing resources

The result of all these efforts has been amazing: 15 conopuddlers, 24 rice hull stoves, 100 new model plows, and 50 sets of plow accessories have been ordered and sold in Mahajanga Province during the first 18 months of the work.

Dr. Gaudreau, who is optimistic that even more farmers will benefit from this unique endeavor of so many diverse partners, expects more linkages to be established in the future.

“After all, we can only go forward from here,” the scientist says positively. ■

Mr. Marc Bergeron, regional coordinator for the French NGO FERT, is part of a highly successful program that supplies credit to farmers.

United Nations volunteer Mr. Pamphile Sinha (brown shirt) works closely with employees of a private-sector agricultural machinery company.

Japan-IRRI Shuttle sparks teamwork

Temperate and tropical rice scientists team up in successful shuttle research between Japan and IRRI.

Dr. John Sheehy of IRRI (left) and Prof. T. Horie of Kyoto University are using models to investigate the effects of global climate change on rice yields.

The Government of Japan has long been one of IRRI's most generous financial supporters. And for the past 7 years, it has been sharing resources that are in some ways more precious than money: its scientists and advanced research facilities.

Through the innovative Japan-IRRI Shuttle Program, more than 40 scientists from Japan and IRRI have collaborated on 47 diverse research projects since 1990.

Both Japan and IRRI have comparative advantages from which the other can benefit: Japan has a large scientific community focusing on basic rice research, excellent facilities, and sophisticated analytical equipment; IRRI has highly trained research teams and centralized tropical research facilities.

The Shuttle has truly been a win-win situation for all concerned. "It's contributing much to the internationalization of the rice research community in Japan, and IRRI scientists get new ideas and advanced knowledge from Japanese participants," says Mr. Tokio Imbe, Shuttle deputy coordinator at IRRI.

Evolving collaboration

The original idea for the Shuttle came about in the late 1980s as a means to enable Japanese scientists to work at IRRI without having to leave their posts for more than 1 month at a time. Scientists from both Japan and IRRI would regularly shuttle back and forth over several years.

This brainstorm became the Japan-IRRI Shuttle Program in 1990, when the Government of Japan agreed to formally fund the link

between IRRI and Japanese scientists. The Shuttle has two basic components, the major one being collaboration of Japanese and IRRI scientists on projects complementary to IRRI's work plan and the other, graduate student research.

To participate, a scientist from Japan or IRRI wishing to use the facilities in either place for up to 3 months per year must submit a research proposal. Project coordinators then identify a counterpart scientist at the host institution, and the Shuttle provides funding for travel and research.

Scientists from 12 Japanese institutions have participated. Research projects have ranged from molecular analysis and diagnosis of rice tungro viruses to a study on the effects of population pressure, rice intensification, and economic development in a Philippine village.

"The ideas being promoted by the Shuttle—cooperation, sharing of expertise and materials, exchange of information—are beneficial for both scientists of Japan and at IRRI. By collaborating, we learn from each other's work," says Dr. Atsushi Yoshimura of Kyushu University, who has been using molecular markers to analyze and pyramid genes for resistance to bacterial blight. "It's wonderful to see us all, coming from different organizations and working as one team."

From IRRI's perspective, the Shuttle has provided excellent opportunities for the professional development of its scientists—particularly those on its nationally recruited staff. To date, eight Filipino researchers have gone to Japan through the Program. One of them, Ms. Jeanie Yanoria, a research assistant in IRRI's Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division, received training in blast research at the National Agricultural Research Center in Tsukuba.

"To be exposed to Japan's research community is an extremely worthwhile experience," says Ms. Yanoria. "I learned new techniques and skills that will be very useful in our project at IRRI."

For Japanese students working on their masters or doctoral degrees, the Shuttle presents a golden opportunity for conducting their thesis research at IRRI. The program supports travel, stipend, and research costs. Each student's adviser is also provided with a once-a-year travel grant to IRRI. Since 1995, five Japanese students have done their thesis research at IRRI.

"Japanese students can learn a great deal by coming to IRRI," emphasizes Dr. Tom Mew, IRRI's

Japanese scholar gains professionally—and personally

"There's so much to write home about," says Tadashi Tsukaguchi, as he puts a lengthy letter to his family in an envelop.

The 27-year-old Ph D scholar from Kyoto University says he wants to share every detail about his 9-month stay at IRRI: from how he enjoys the tropical climate, to stories about new friends from all over the world, to life in the dormitory, to the extremely supportive IRRI scientists who are helping him with his research.

"By working with scientists at IRRI, I am gaining many insights into my research field," explains the scholar, who is trying to determine the maximum yield potential of rice in the dry season and the factors that limit grain filling.

But in some ways even more valuable to Mr. Tsukaguchi than his increased scientific knowledge is how much he has grown as a person—and the many new friends he has made.

"The international environment has made me feel comfortable with people from different cultures," says the scholar. "I'm now seeing the world from a different angle."

L. Sayo

Shuttle coordinator. "In addition to gaining valuable experience in tropical rice research, they are also exposed to IRRI's multicultural environment—which contributes to their personal development." (See sidebar.)

Continuing enthusiasm

The high degree of interaction among scientists from Japan and IRRI in achieving common research objectives is the Shuttle's main achievement. Although now in its third phase, scientists remain enthused about the Shuttle, as evident from the 30 new proposals submitted for funding in 1996; 23 were selected.

The Japan-IRRI Shuttle has proven to be an effective mechanism for maximizing resources and fostering cooperation in rice research. An additional benefit has been the training of young scientists, who will some day assume leadership in the rice research community. ■

Coping with too much water

A long-running Thai-based partnership is creating deepwater rice plants that thrive in the floodwater.

“What we need is a rice plant that can breathe when fully immersed underwater.”

This vision of Dr. Panatda Bhekasut, a plant breeder and physiologist with the Thai-IRRI Deepwater Rice Research Project, may some day become a reality in the world's deepwater rice areas—thanks to the efforts of a committed team of scientists based in Thailand and throughout South and Southeast Asia.

Dr. Bhekasut and her colleagues believe that the deepwater rice plant's coping mechanisms for surviving underwater—rather than its ability to elongate its stems to keep its foliage above the floodwaters—may be the secret to stabilizing yields on the 9 million hectares of deepwater riceland in Asia.

Why deepwater rice research?

Deepwater rice means life to more than 100 million Asians. For them, there is no food other than rice that can meet their basic dietary needs. But rice yields on these lands are low, averaging from 0.5 to 2.5 tons per hectare. And in some years—because of severe flooding—there is no harvest.

Increasing the annual rice harvest in deepwater areas is a critical social and economic challenge. The millions of people who must survive in these flood-prone regions are generally among the poorest in the world.

Because of the diversity of the flood-prone areas, no one research organization can possibly solve all of the problems. Collaboration and partnership are the keys to acting locally and thinking globally.

For many years, Thailand has been the main base for collaborative efforts in deepwater rice research. Way back in 1941, the country recognized the importance of deepwater rice research

by building the Huntra Rice Experiment Station. In 1975, the Prachinburi Rice Research Center (see map) was established. It is now one of the leading centers in the region for deepwater rice research because of its excellent facilities and experienced staff (see sidebar, p 18).

The research effort became truly international when, in 1974, IRRI decided to direct its deepwater rice program from Thailand and to help fi-

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nance Thai efforts. This partnership was strengthened in 1991 when Thailand and IRRI signed a memorandum of understanding for regional research on deepwater rice. Through this agreement, most of IRRI's deepwater rice breeding activities were transferred to Thailand; emphasis was also placed on regional research and training efforts.

As a result, Thai scientists are working with their counterparts from IRRI to develop and exchange deepwater rice breeding lines and associated technologies with scientists in Bangladesh, Cambodia, India, Myanmar, and Vietnam.

Scientists from these countries come to Thailand to observe experiments, discuss breeding techniques, and make selections. And each year, Thai scientists visit researchers in the other countries to coordinate work and assist in selecting breeding materials. IRRI researchers support scientists from the national agricultural research sys-

tems (NARS) with inputs from strategic research done at the Institute's Philippine headquarters and through staff members based in Thailand.

Motivating through teamwork

These initiatives of the deepwater rice research scientists have the goal of improving productivity of rice and integrating it into sustainable production systems that improve the well-being of farm families.

Most of the field research is done in collaboration with NARS scientists in Bangladesh, Cambodia, India, Myanmar, Thailand, and Vietnam. By working together, the strengths of NARS in local research are linked with the strategic global research activities of IRRI and other advanced laboratories. Through this collaboration, NARS scientists can work on research that directly benefits local farmers.

Dr. Panatda Bhekasut inspects the panicles of deepwater rice plants at the Prachinburi Rice Research Center in Thailand.

“There are many good scientists in the NARS, but their potentials need to be nurtured,” Dr. Bhekasut explains. “Because they work with few resources, they need IRRI to initiate collaborative activities that can make use of their experiences.”

She adds, “IRRI needs to continue being the source of knowledge—a place where scientists can be trained and get information on new technologies.”

The entire deepwater rice research community seems to have internalized a positive, cooperative spirit that is reflected in the attitude of Dr. Donald Puckridge, IRRI’s representative to the Thai-IRRI Deepwater Rice Research Project from 1981 until his retirement in 1996 (see sidebar).

“Don always referred to projects as *our* work. He would remind us that what we are doing is not Thai or IRRI work but *our* work,” emphasizes Dr. Bhekasut.

Sharing germplasm—and experience

Everyone wins when scientists from different countries collaborate. One of the major thrusts has been in exchanging germplasm, which can help scientists develop deepwater rice varieties that consistently produce higher yields.

Germplasm from India, for example, has outstanding submergence tolerance and elongation ability. Rices from Myanmar have big panicles, few nonproductive tillers (stems), and do not fall down easily. And Thai rices have good grain quality.

“We all benefit, so why not share?” asks Dr. Tawee Kupkanchanakul, an agronomist at the Thai Rice Research Institute, Department of Agriculture of Thailand, who has worked with the Thai-IRRI Project for many years. In addition to

Scientists working in national deepwater rice programs are informally linked with the strategic global research activities of IRRI and advanced laboratories.

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International spirit at Prachinburi

The Prachinburi Rice Research Center has become well connected internationally, according to Dr. Donald Puckridge, IRRI’s representative to the Thai-IRRI Deepwater Rice Research Project for 15 years.

The seasoned deepwater rice scientist thinks that the Center can truly help accelerate the development of deepwater rice research in other Asian countries.

“When I was at Prachinburi last Friday,” he said, “there was a group from China and a group from Korea visiting the Mekong project that distributes plant breeding materials to Myanmar, Cambodia, and Vietnam.

“And just recently a scientist from the University of Western Australia conducted a training course on submergence tolerance that was quite relevant to a European Union-funded project involving India, Thailand, Singapore, United Kingdom, and IRRI. And there was a Japanese scientist out there working on wild rice.”

This international, cooperative spirit bodes well for the future of deepwater rice research.

germplasm exchange, scientists are cooperating in other ways. For example, Thai scientists are learning the technique of dry season rice cultivation in deepwater areas from scientists of South Asia. In return, Thai scientists are sharing with researchers from other Asian countries the experience they have gained in improving varieties.

Formalizing regional collaboration

Some of the Thai researchers think that IRRI scientists are in a better position to evaluate the strengths and shortcomings of deepwater rice research in collaborating countries.

“Because IRRI scientists travel more than the NARS scientists, they see more. And when you see more, you get more information that can help you sort out what technology can be adapted to a particular country,” says Dr. Kupkanchanakul.

Drs. Bhekasut and Kupkanchanakul think there is a need to formalize the collaboration among scientists from the different countries who are working in deepwater rice.

“What IRRI has initiated is good but it is still informal,” asserts Dr. Kupkanchanakul. “If we have a consortium, the scientists can work with

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the full support of their supervisors because their mandate would be clearly spelled out.”

Meeting the challenges

The annual flooding in deepwater areas truly makes producing rice a challenge. Varieties and cropping systems must be adapted to the extremely varied environmental conditions, and often, technologies developed for other rice ecosystems are not relevant for deepwater areas.

“Unlike irrigated rice, the problems in producing deepwater rice are extremely complex and vary from year to year. In 1996, for example, the promising line SPRAE76Com3-5-2 performed very well with an average yield of 4 tons per hectare. But in 1995 its yield and quality were not as good,” says Dr. Prayote Charoendham, director of the Prachinburi Rice Research Center.

With only one crop a year, developing deepwater rice varieties is slow. Progress, however, has been made: methods for screening for elongation ability have been developed, and resistance to pests and tolerance for submergence,

drought, acidity, and salinity have been incorporated into varieties.

Prototypes of the new plant type with deepwater survival mechanisms are being tested extensively in the field. The major objective of the collaborative breeding program is to develop a range of rice varieties that can guarantee yields of 3-4 tons per hectare.

“In the future, more productivity will be needed from this ecosystem because you cannot expect much more increase from irrigated rice, and rainfed lowland rice production is constrained by drought and poor soil fertility,” Dr. Kupkanchanakul projects. “But the fertility in the deepwater rice areas is high. The problem is simply too much water.”

Dr. Kupkanchanakul is confident that collaborative research efforts among the scientists from national systems in South and Southeast Asia, advanced scientific institutions, and IRRI can stabilize yields on the flood-prone lands by creating rice plants that can cope with too much water. ■

Thai agronomist Dr. Tawee Kupkanchanakul (left) and Dr. Donald Puckridge of IRRI talk about new deepwater rice varieties at the Huntra Rice Experiment Station in Thailand.

Reducing the risks in rainfed lowland rice

Scientists use a consortium to achieve research success in the rainfed lowlands.

Thai scientists at the Ubon Ratchathani Rice Research Center are sharing information on drought tolerance with their Consortium counterparts.

Perhaps nowhere on the face of the earth are farmers braver than those who eke out a living on Asia's rainfed lowlands. Described as "risky and unpredictable," this diverse environment is far from ideal for growing any crop. A field that produces a good crop one season may be flooded or stricken by drought the next.

Yields are often disappointing, with the 40 million hectares of rainfed lowlands in South and Southeast Asia producing, on average, 2.3 tons per hectare and contributing only 18 percent of the global rice harvest.

As population balloons and irrigated rice areas shrink, rainfed lowland farmers will be under increasing pressure to grow more rice. Delays in finding ways to boost production could be devastating for both rice consumers and farmers.

Fortunately, a group of determined, like-minded scientists from IRRI and around Asia is working to systematically address the constraints in this environment—and toward genuinely improving the lives of some of the world's poorest people.

Consortium achieves quicker results

To tackle the problems in such a complex ecosystem requires scientists from many institutions and countries to work as part of a coordinated effort.

In 1991, IRRI and the national agricultural research systems (NARS) in Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Philippines, and Thailand established the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium with funding from the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and the Government of The Netherlands.

“Through the Consortium, research work has been consolidated and mechanisms developed to share appropriate technologies—locally, regionally, and internationally—that increase rice yields and the incomes of rainfed lowland farmers,” says Dr. Colin Piggin, IRRI agronomist and program leader for rainfed lowland rice ecosystem research.

“Research results come a lot quicker if countries work together instead of in isolation, which is the essence of the Consortium,” says Mr. Nopporn Supapoj, director of the Ubon Ratchathani Rice Research Center in Thailand and member of the Consortium steering committee.

The Consortium’s true strengths are that it takes the research to where the production constraints are—and the work is done in partnership with the scientists who know these places best.

“Seven key sites (see map) have been identified where there is a major area of rainfed lowland and a well-qualified institution with interested staff members capable of doing strategic research to address the issues,” explains Dr. Len Wade, IRRI rainfed lowland agronomist.

Themes—such as drought and sustainability—are major research issues for the ecosystem and address strategic and applied issues. A series of workshops on theme-based research results was held in 1996; selected scientific papers from these will comprise a special issue of *Experimental Agriculture* in 1998.

Commitment key to research progress

Commitment to the Consortium’s mission—from scientists to research managers to policy makers—is the key to its success.

Dr. Elias L. Calacal, president of Mariano Marcos State University (MMSU) in the Philippines—the lead institution for the Consortium’s research on sustainability issues—is an example of a steadfast supporter.

“We are confident that through the Consortium, strong partnerships are being developed around Asia,” Dr. Calacal says. “The research results generated by MMSU can be used in other rainfed lowland areas in the region.”

The benefits from the Consortium are many. Administrators of NARS, for example, have been prompted to invest substantially in new infrastructure, additional personnel, and equipment.

Professional collegiality among IRRI and NARS scientists has increased and training pro-

grams and workshops have strengthened the research capacity of NARS scientists.

Multidisciplinary teams—a new way of doing things for many institutions—have also been created.

“The IRRI-sponsored training programs our scientists attend have enhanced their knowledge and skills in doing quality research work,” says Dr. Achmad M. Fagi, director of the Central Research Institute for Food Crops in Indonesia.

“These efforts ensure that NARS scientists are equipped to conduct strategic research of regional relevance,” Dr. Piggin says. “Additionally, government policy makers have been sensitized and made aware of the potential for impact in the rainfed lowlands.”

This is certainly true for Indonesia, where Dr. Fagi says that, with or without funding from the Consortium, rainfed lowland research will continue with support from the Government.

Review emphasizes Consortium success

A major review of the Consortium was conducted by ADB in 1994, with the reviewers agreeing that the Consortium has been effective in encouraging collaboration and in providing excellent research on the ecosystem’s major constraints.

“With IRRI and NARS scientists working together in targeted environments, collaboration and partnership are being strengthened,” says Dr. Piggin. “This is resulting in increased research efficiency and more widely applicable results.”

Sustainable higher rice production is an achievable goal. The world—through the Consortium—must take advantage of the opportunities offered by the rainfed lowlands. ■

France and IRRI: symbiosis in research

Collaboration among French and IRRI scientists has evolved into a special alliance that particularly benefits upland farmers.

Within a few years of IRRI's founding in 1960, French scientists were already informally collaborating with the Institute's researchers. At that time, no one probably could have foreseen the splendid partnership that would develop—and the impact it would have on rice research.

Since 1978, IRRI has received the services of resident French researchers equivalent to more than 36 person-years of senior-level scientist time, estimated to be worth more than US\$3.5 million. France has also been a solid financial supporter of the Institute over the years. The French Government's steadfast commitment to rice research is obvious—as is that of the individual scientists.

"The agricultural research to which IRRI contributes is the most important in the world—simply because it's about working on the world's most important food crop," says Dr. Serge Savary, an IRRI internationally recruited staff member seconded from the Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopération (ORSTOM) who specializes in plant disease epidemiology.

Lengthy, productive collaboration

French institutions have been involved in both temperate and tropical rice research for more than 70 years. In recent times, French scientists have worked in rice research worldwide, studying a diversity of topics. Three main French institutions have collaborated with IRRI:

- The Annual Crops Department of the Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD-CA), which conducts research and development studies in the tropics and subtropics, with a focus on crops.
- ORSTOM, which carries out basic research that targets development in tropical regions.

- Institut national de la recherche agronomique (INRA), which primarily conducts research on rice under Mediterranean conditions, although it has a few programs in Vietnam.

A unique form of symbiosis has evolved between France and IRRI. Dr. Savary explains it from the ORSTOM perspective: "IRRI benefits from the collaborative efforts because there is ensured continuity in research, with ORSTOM providing staff to do basic research. For ORSTOM, IRRI provides a platform to carry out its mandate and work in Asian countries—with no loss of identity." The same is true for CIRAD.

An Agreement of Cooperation signed in September 1986 formalized IRRI's relationship with the three institutions. Collaborative meetings between IRRI and the Inter-organization Committee (CIRAD-INRA-ORSTOM or CIO) have been held every other year since then to review current work and to discuss future collaborative programs. In 1995, IRRI signed a Memorandum of Understanding with CIRAD-CA and a Protocol of Agreement with ORSTOM.

Making important contributions to science

Since 1978, France has posted 12 researchers at IRRI. Six are currently on board, two of them working as shuttle researchers and four as internationally recruited staff members at IRRI headquarters in the Philippines.

"France's most important contribution to rice science has been to provide people to do the research," explains Dr. Brigitte Courtois, an upland rice breeder seconded to IRRI from CIRAD-CA.

A significant portion of their efforts is focused on the upland rice ecosystem, where France—because of its historical presence in West Africa and the importance of upland rice there—has a comparative advantage.

Strategic, long-term research is also a priority, with scientists currently working on two main

projects: a risk analysis of rice pests at the Asian tropical region scale, and development of methodologies for in situ germplasm conservation.

"The strategic research essentially addresses risk: the risk associated with rice pests in an ever-changing agricultural environment and the risk of genetic erosion of rice germplasm worldwide," explains Dr. Savary. "This research has a strong ecoregional connotation, and it reflects new paradigms that French institutions and IRRI have simultaneously, and interactively, adopted."

In most cases, France has provided IRRI with financial support and the scientists to do the research in partnership with colleagues at both IRRI and in national agricultural research systems.

Highlights of collaborative activities

Scientific cooperation with IRRI has focused on evaluating and sharing genetic resources, breeding improved upland rice varieties, rice crop protection, nitrogen fixation and soil fertility, and characterizing cropping systems.

French scientists have taken the lead at IRRI since 1983 in breeding improved upland rice varieties. A recent thrust has been to develop varieties through farmer participatory breeding.

"By involving farmers at different breeding steps, we hope to develop varieties that are more acceptable to them and to define the best methodology to do it," explains Dr. Courtois.

Another important research area has focused on evaluating genetic resources using isozyme technology and molecular markers, and improving rice varieties. In the field of microbiology, the contribution of the photosynthetic biomass in rice water has been extensively studied.

Characterizing, analyzing, and improving upland and rainfed lowland cropping and farming systems in Southeast Asia have also been a research thrust.

New dimension for partnership

In late 1997, representatives of the CIO and IRRI will meet to discuss their partnership, which Dr. Savary predicts will take on a new dimension.

"Rather than a partnership, the term 'alliance' seems more appropriate because CIO and IRRI will probably tighten their links further," he says.

Strategic issues of the Asian region will capture the bulk of the discussions, which will focus on developing a new set of research programs—many of which are part of the ecoregional initiative led by IRRI. France has already significantly contributed to shaping this initiative that aims to help ensure the long-term sustainability of agricultural systems in Asia.

Through partnerships like the France-IRRI collaboration, researchers are truly making a difference in the lives of the world's rice farmers and consumers. ■

French rice breeder Dr. Brigitte Courtois (right) and her IRRI colleagues, Ms. Tatiana Borobo and Ms. Wenefie Petalcorin, discuss recombinant inbred line populations being used to map genes for drought tolerance.

Keeping South Asia's granary bountiful

Diversity provides strength to the Rice-Wheat Consortium, which is tackling the awesome challenge of feeding more than 350 million people.

Rice and wheat. This amazingly productive combination feeds South Asia's masses. But for how much longer will these two vital cereal crops be able to nourish the more than 350 million people who depend on them?

Since the late 1980s, scientists have been concerned that the 12 million-hectare regional granary, which cuts across Pakistan, India, Nepal, and Bangladesh, may some day wear out—with horrific consequences.

Improving productivity and ensuring the sustainability of the rice-wheat system—and with it the fate of millions of people—has become the mission of a dedicated group of regional and international scientists.

Working together, taking initiatives

Collaboration among diverse partners from national and international organizations is the key to solving local problems through global action. A substantial effort was mobilized in May 1994 when leaders of the national agricultural research systems (NARS) of the four countries launched the Rice-Wheat Consortium for the Indo-Gangetic Plains.

The strength of the Consortium lies in the differences of its members: the national systems of the four countries and four centers of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research: Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo (CIMMYT), International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics

R. Cabrera

(ICRISAT), International Irrigation Management Institute (IIMI), and IRRI. Cornell University is also participating.

The national system of China participates as an associate member—primarily because the country's 10 million rice-wheat hectares comprise a different system than that of South Asia.

Although young, the Consortium has already held successful traveling seminars, workshops, and training courses. Its efforts have been responsible for progress in the timely establishment of the wheat crop in some parts of India by using locally manufactured reduced and zero-tillage equipment.

Even more important than the technical accomplishments to date is that scientists in the region have become proactive.

"This Consortium is truly NARS-driven, which, to me, is very healthy," says Consortium Facilitator Inder Pal Abrol, who works out of ICRISAT's New Delhi office. "NARS are taking the initiative and not just reacting to the suggestions of well-meaning outsiders."

Through these efforts, scientists are preparing to tackle a huge challenge: how to increase rice-wheat production by improving input-use efficiency, without harming the fragile environment.

Mysterious yield declines

The Green Revolution of the late 1960s made planting wheat after rice popular in South Asia. The promise of producing more grain more quickly made the new high-yielding, short-duration varieties extremely attractive to farmers. Along with the new seed came chemical fertilizers, irrigation, and pesticides.

Thirty years later, rice and wheat are the most important crops in the region. They supply about 80 percent of the cereals people eat, and for many of the poorest, much of their income. The rice-wheat cropping pattern, which provides 25 percent of the region's rice and 33 percent of its wheat, covers 32 percent of the rice area and 42 percent of the wheat area (see map).

In the mid-1980s scientists noticed a frightening phenomenon on the region's experiment stations. Yields were mysteriously declining in long-term rice-wheat trials—even as inputs were kept constant. Scientists at CIMMYT and IRRI took this warning sign seriously, which led to the first collaborative surveys of farmers and their practices in the four countries in 1990.

Other problems add to the complexity: poor irrigation practices have degraded the land, and soil fertility seems to be gradually decreasing. Insects, diseases, and weeds cause more damage with each crop. To make matters worse, there is simply no more land for new fields. Farmers in the rice-wheat belt already plant nearly every scrap of suitable land. Increased productivity must come from existing fields.

Tackling sustainable yields

One of the most perplexing things is that researchers still do not have solid scientific proof that the yield declines recorded on the experi-

J. Lazaro/M. Wenceslao

G. Hettler

Rice and wheat feed South Asia's masses.

Drs. Kevin Bronson, Peter Hobbs, and Inder Pal Abrol of the Rice-Wheat Consortium discuss research progress in a wheat plot at IRRI headquarters in the Philippines.

ment stations are actually happening in farmers' fields in any kind of pattern. They only have farmers' perceptions of this phenomenon.

In any case, the declines generally seem to be most pronounced in rice and in areas where yields were previously the highest.

"Farmers in some places are saying that every year they have to increase the amount of fertilizer they apply—just to maintain yields," Dr. Abrol says.

One Consortium scientist, however, believes that it doesn't really matter whether farmers are or are not experiencing yield declines.

"Farmers have to increase overall cereal production by 2.5 percent per year to keep pace with population growth in the region," says Dr. Peter Hobbs, a CIMMYT agronomist based in Kathmandu, Nepal, who has worked with rice and wheat since the 1980s when a formal consortium was only a dream. "Yield declines at certain sites are just part of the equation."

He stresses that the Consortium must address the same issues regardless of whether it is trying to reverse declines or to increase yields—and this will take sustainable funding.

Motivation through cooperation

The only way to tackle these challenges in the rice-wheat system is through a unified, focused effort using a systems perspective. It must involve all key research partners, who bring with them their unique backgrounds and strengths, materials, and a true spirit of cooperation.

For example, Bangladesh's comparative advantage lies with sharing its experiences in growing boro (dry season irrigated) rice using shallow tubewells. This could "bring a boon" to eastern India and Nepal, according to Dr. Craig Meisner, a CIMMYT agronomist based in Dhaka.

Pakistani scientists, in collaboration with CIMMYT researchers, have been contributing from the start. "We are taking the lead in developing technologies for wheat following rice—such as zero-tillage—that farmers in India and Nepal could easily adopt," says Dr. Abdul Majid, wheat coordinator of Pakistan's National Agricultural Research Center.

India obviously has the strongest national agricultural research program. Scientists from Nepal and Bangladesh are benefiting from studying at Indian institutions, going to training courses, and

completing graduate work. In addition to scientific expertise—particularly in crop modeling—Nepal has a vast wealth of genetic diversity in both rice and wheat to share with its neighbors.

The role of the scientists from the international centers is primarily to guide and provide technical backstopping in specific areas for the NARS scientists. CIMMYT researchers, for instance, handle tillage efficiency and crop establishment, and IRRI scientists focus on nutrient management and integrated pest management.

By working as a team, scientists are identifying technologies that will improve productivity in the rice-wheat system—sustainably and quickly.

Collaborating despite differences

Through the Consortium, scientists have drastically changed the way they do things—and with whom they work. Rice scientists are working with wheat scientists, and researchers from national systems are cooperating with those from international centers.

Wheat and rice scientists as partners.

Until a few years ago, agronomists Muhammad Badaruddin and Abu Sowar Jahan, from the Wheat Research Centre near Nashipur in northwestern Bangladesh, used to collaborate only with other wheat researchers. But not anymore. Scientists from other national systems and from IRRI—such as soil fertility specialist Kevin Bronson—are now their partners, too.

As the three colleagues walk through the center's well-groomed fields of swaying green wheat and triticale, they freely toss around ideas on nutrient management in the rice-wheat rotation.

"We think retaining mungbean stubble will be a significantly better practice—especially in providing a residual effect on the rice crop," explains Mr. Sowar Jahan as he describes a wheat-mungbean-rice rotation experiment.

"How will you convince farmers not to remove the stubble for cattle fodder?" Dr. Bronson asks.

"If farmers get at least a crop of edible beans first, we believe that they can be persuaded to leave the stubble for incorporating into the soil," Dr. Badaruddin replies.

All three seem excited about their work.

Training scientists in modeling. At IRRI headquarters in the Philippines, Dr. Jagadish Timsina, a systems agronomist and modeler at

Tribhuvan University in Nepal, surveys his class of 18 agronomists, physiologists, and soil scientists from the four Consortium countries. All are novices, but after 5 days of intensive training, they will have the basic know-how to become the core of a rice-wheat modeling network.

Consortium leaders saw from the beginning the importance of exposing rice-wheat scientists to systems approaches for conducting research. The idea definitely has appeal—and practicality. Through modeling, scientists can think on a global level while working to solve local problems.

"This modeling network will facilitate interaction and encourage participants to apply their skills," says Dr. Timsina, who is also involved in an Australia-Bangladesh bilateral project to build capacity in national systems—including the Wheat Research Centre at Nashipur.

Optimistic about the future

The Consortium is being heralded as a model ecoregional initiative where a cadre of CGIAR centers, NARS, and other institutions work together in solving a complex problem.

Dr. Bronson and his colleagues are optimistic about the future. "By including the farmers in our efforts, I feel that we are well on track to making sure that South Asia's rice and wheat granary keeps pace with its growing population." ■

Dr. Jagadish Timsina points out a computer modeling concept to Rice-Wheat Consortium scientists during a training course at IRRI.

G. Hettel

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

Research that makes a difference

Between now and 2025, 1.4 billion new rice consumers will be added to the earth. To feed these people, farmers must grow an additional 10 million tons of rice every year.

How?

Accelerating rice research efforts is the only way to ensure that these people will not go hungry. Because of the magnitude of this endeavor, no one organization can do it all. A truly global effort is needed.

IRRI long ago recognized the power of partnerships, with the Institute's scientists and support staff actively collaborating for years with diverse partners in the developing and developed worlds.

The program highlights that follow reflect how IRRI and its partners are successfully conducting relevant research and research-related activities. The endeavors described are all part of a major plan to meet the challenges of how to significantly boost rice production through sustainable practices in the face of an ever-increasing population, static or even decreasing land and labor resources, and declining aid from traditional donors. ■

Scientists from national systems and IRRI are working with farmers to achieve common goals in rice research.

C. Dedolph

Irrigated rice

IRRIGATED RICE GROWS in banded, puddled fields with an assured water supply for one or more crops a year. Worldwide, 79 million hectares of irrigated rice (54 percent of the total rice area) produce about three quarters of all the rice harvested. Average yields vary from 3 to 9 tons per hectare. Generally, farmers of irrigated land use more purchased inputs than farmers of nonirrigated land. Improved rice cultivars that have been developed for irrigated ricelands are of short duration, nitrogen responsive, and have multiple resistances to insect pests and diseases and some tolerance for adverse soils.

Milestone marked in long-term experiment

The 100th rice crop was planted in May 1997 in the long-term continuous cropping experiment at IRRI.

Having produced three crops a year since 1963, the IRRI plot is the world's most intensive ricefield. The 34-year-old experiment was set up to determine the effects of intensive cropping on rice productivity and yield sustainability. Today, rice yields in the plots are similar to those 100 crops ago; the one difference is that more fertilizer needs to be applied to achieve the same yield level.

Five years ago, however, the yields were not the same as those obtained at the start. Possible causes were identified, such as new soil pests, excessive pesticides, and fertilizer deficiency.

After exploring each of these possibilities, scientists discovered that the soil health has been changing. The

Scientists get mud between their toes while celebrating the planting of the 100th rice crop in the long-term continuous cropping experiment at IRRI headquarters.

continuous irrigation and cropping may have altered the chemical properties of soil organic matter, which is the major source of nitrogen from soils to plants. These soils no longer supply nitrogen in the same pattern over the growing season as before.

"To cope with this, not only the amount of fertilizer, but also the timing of its application should be modified," explains Dr. Osamu Ito, head of IRRI's Agronomy, Plant Physiology, and Agroecology Division.

Scientists from IRRI and national agricultural research systems are continuing to clarify the long-term effect of crop intensification on rice production by conducting multidisciplinary studies on a range of subjects.

Intensive rice systems with two—and sometimes three—crops per year are the dominant food production systems in the irrigated lowlands of tropical and subtropical Asia. More than 1 billion rice farmers and urban consumers depend on them.

"We hope that through these experiments, we can ensure the permanency of the millions of hectares of irrigated rice in Asia," Dr. Ito says.

Curbing methane emissions from ricefields

Human activities—including rice production—are changing the world's climate.

"Flooded ricefields produce methane, which is the second most important greenhouse gas after carbon dioxide," explains Dr. Reiner Wassmann, a biologist seconded from the Fraunhofer Institute. He and Ms. Rhoda Lantin, IRRI senior associate scientist, are coordinating an international network of scientists that is working to substantially broaden the database on methane emissions from ricefields at sites in Indonesia and Thailand, and at two sites each in China, India, and the Philippines.

"Continuous flooding is generally associated with high emission rates throughout irrigated ricefields in Southeast and East Asia," Dr. Wassmann says. "But if farmers drain their fields early in the cropping cycle for a brief time, methane emission rates can be more than halved."

The scientists are developing viable mitigation options to provide a basis for future decisions and technology development by policy makers, agriculturists, environmentalists, and rice producers.

G. Hettel

Automated chambers at sites around Asia are being used to measure methane emissions from ricefields.

Low-cost rice dryer a success in Vietnam

The true measure of the success of a new agricultural technology is whether farmers are willing to buy it. Using this criterion, the innovative SRR-1 rice dryer is doing well. During the first 18 months after its release in August 1995, about 300 farmers in southern Vietnam bought dryers for US\$70—with no subsidies.

“I believe this is the first farm-level rice dryer to become commercially successful,” says Mr. Martin Gummert, IRRI consultant and project coordinator of the German-funded project Post-harvest Technologies for Rice in the Humid Tropics, who has provided support and technical backstopping.

Why?

“Because it’s cheap!” he exclaims. “A farmer can afford it without applying for a loan.”

Although many farm-level dryer prototypes have been built over the years, none have been truly successful because small-scale farmers cannot afford them. This new dryer, however, was designed with its users in mind. Its creators, Vietnamese agricultural engineers Drs. Phan Hieu Hien and Le Van Ban of the University of Agriculture and Forestry in Ho Chi Minh City, took a proven low-temperature drying principle

provided by IRRI and then built the cheapest dryer possible. They called it the SRR-1, which means “very low cost” in Vietnamese.

The beauty of the dryer is in its simplicity: an electric motor and a fan set on top of a duct running through a large bin made of bamboo matting. Ambient or slightly warm air circulates through the bin to dry the rice. During the wet season, a simple coal stove supplies supplemental heat. The SRR-1 can dry a 1-ton batch of rice in 2 to 4 days, with the drying costing only about 5 percent of the crop’s value. The SRR-1 dryer totally removes the risks and the high labor associated with sun drying.

Dryer prototypes are being further tested and adapted to local conditions in Bangladesh, India, and Myanmar through the Crop and Resource Management Network and through two national organizations in the Philippines.

Surmounting a challenge with the new plant type

On most fronts, progress has been steady in perfecting the new plant type (NPT) rices for irrigated environments. However, researchers are encountering an unforeseen challenge—poor grain filling—that is preventing the plants from expressing their yield potential.

“This obstacle is requiring us to modify some of our approaches for developing the NPT,” explains Dr. Gurdev Khush, principal plant breeder at IRRI. “This additional work will slightly delay getting these plants into farmers’ fields by the turn of the century—our original target.”

Physiological factors contributing to poor grain filling of tropical japonica rice have been identified, including compact arrangement of spikelets on the panicle branches, lack of apical dominance, and limited numbers of vascular bundles when compared with indica germplasm. Breeders are rectifying the problem by selectively incorporating genes from indica parents into tropical japonica germplasm, which was used for developing the NPT.

Other work on the NPT is on track. In 1996, IRRI and national program breeders evaluated many promising breeding lines. Resistance to tungro and brown planthopper is being incorporated and several lines with resistance to blast and bacterial blight were selected. Major strides have also been made in improving grain quality.

Many new crosses were also made to broaden the germplasm base. “Most of the parents used in developing the NPT germplasm are from Indonesia,” explains Dr. Khush. Parents from the Philippines, Thailand, and India have now been used to improve the grain quality and introduce genes for disease and insect resistance.

“We are confident that we will be able to overcome the problem of grain filling and develop many NPT lines with acceptable grain quality and multiple resistance to diseases and insects. These breeding materials will be continuously shared with our national program partners,” says the plant breeder. ■

Rainfed lowland rice

RAINFED LOWLAND RICE grows in banded fields that are flooded for at least part of the cropping season to water depths that may exceed 50 centimeters for no more than 10 consecutive days. Worldwide, 36 million hectares of rice make up about 25 percent of the total rice area. Rainfed lowlands are characterized by a lack of water control, with floods and drought being potential problems. Adverse climate, poor soils, and a lack of suitable modern technologies keep farmers from increasing productivity.

Rice-chickpea patterns boost farmers' incomes

Until recently, as many as 1 million hectares of land often remained fallow following the wet season rice crop in northwestern Bangladesh. Although this region receives 1,200-1,400 millimeters of annual rainfall, nearly all of it comes between June and September, and much of it runs off the surface. A quick-drying surface soil and a hard plowpan limit crop establishment and growth after the wet season without irrigation.

Enter early-maturing rice varieties and chickpea—a deep rooted crop, which if established soon after an early rice harvest, is able to produce respectable yields on residual moisture.

“Short-duration rice varieties for the wet season have permitted the cultivation of short-duration chickpea and the intensification of the region’s cropping system,” says Dr. Nur E. Elahi, leader of the cropping systems group at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI).

Because chickpea commands a good market price, farmers are rapidly adopting rice-chickpea cropping patterns even though more research still needs to be done. “We must improve

C. Diederich

crop establishment and weed control for direct seeding,” says Dr. M.A. Mazid, the Rajshahi site coordinator for the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium (RLRRC). “We must also understand the system’s nutrient and water balance.”

“The release in 1996 of Brridhan 32, an early-maturing rice variety (125-130 days) was the first major breakthrough in giving farmers in Bangladesh additional time to establish their chickpea crop,” says Dr. M.A. Salam, rice breeder at Rajshahi and RLRRC theme coordinator for population improvement.

A real boon for the rice-chickpea patterns will be the imminent release of Brridhan 33, which has an even shorter duration than Brridhan 32. “Farmers will be able to cut about 10-15 days off the rice-growing season, which should improve soil moisture for growing chickpea after the wet season,” Dr. Salam concludes.

Tapping farmers' knowledge in rice breeding

In the vast rainfed lowland areas of eastern India, resource-poor rice farmers often grow two or three proven traditional varieties as insurance against flooding or drought. They know which will survive one or the other of these stresses.

Many modern varieties cannot compete with traditional varieties in adverse conditions—and even when they do, according to Dr. Surapong Sarkarung, IRRI rice breeder, they are not being readily adopted. “Modern varieties that tolerate submergence, for example, often lack other traits that farmers and consumers value in traditional varieties,” he says.

This situation has prompted IRRI scientists to transfer major breeding activities to areas such as eastern India and Thailand that are more representative of lowlands prone to submergence—and using farmers’ inherent experience and

With the arrival of the rains, women in Madagascar transplant rice—a difficult, backbreaking task.

local water regimes—which farmers know best.

“Of course, it is not practical to develop rice varieties for individual villages,” Dr. Sarkarung says, but these trained farmers could form community cooperatives for several villages or districts with similar conditions.”

Improving productivity of direct wet seeding

With the increasing popularity of direct wet seeding of rice throughout Asia (see CREMNET evaluation, p 46), IRRI researchers are looking for ways to increase the productivity of this technique through effective land leveling and bund management.

The root systems that develop in flooded soils are shallow, making it difficult for the plant to reach the water in deeper soil layers late in the season when drought often occurs.

Improved mechanical land leveling is the key to achieving uniform water depth and soil water status—thus alleviating the water supply problem for farmers who direct seed their rice.

Data collected from 50 farms in four Philippine villages show that yields for direct seeded rice were significantly correlated with the precision of land leveling. In field studies conducted over 3 years, farmers, on average, lost 1 ton per hectare in grain yield because of poor land leveling.

“Fields with better land leveling show significantly lower seasonal water stress,” explains Dr. Sadiqul I. Bhuiyan, IRRI water resource specialist. “But as field size increases, land leveling precision decreases. So large fields should be divided by bunds into smaller plots, or greater attention should be paid to precision leveling.” ■

Direct seeding of rice in Cambodia.

perception in the selection process. For submergence-prone lowland areas, farmers are looking for traits found in their traditional varieties, such as tolerance for flash flooding at the seedling stage and good grain quality.

With the help of more than 50 farmers in Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Orissa states, some of the desirable traits in traditional varieties have been successfully incorporated into improved varieties, the early generations of which have already been evaluated.

These farmers, with the assistance of IRRI scientists, are performing a wide array of tasks in evaluating and selecting germplasm. Researchers are convinced this breeding approach facilitates selecting materials specifically adapted to

Upland rice

MANY OF THE WORLD'S poorest farmers live in the uplands of Asia, Africa, and Latin America where farming systems are highly diverse. Most upland farmers still grow traditional varieties without using chemical inputs. More than 19 million hectares of upland rice are grown worldwide—around 63 percent of them in Asia. Upland rice areas are often mountainous, with a lot of steeply sloping land. They do, however, vary in altitude, from highlands of 2,500 meters to gently sloping areas only a few meters above sea level. The defining feature is not altitude but that rice grows on well-drained soils without standing water.

Perennial upland rice: food, erosion control

Traditional slash-and-burn agriculture, with its long fallow periods, has proven sustainable through the centuries for upland farmers. But today, farmers have been shifting to longer cropping periods and shorter fallows due to increased population pressures, accelerating nutrient depletion and soil erosion.

As a solution to the erosion problem, IRRI breeders are working to develop a rice plant that is perennial: one that renews its top growth each season. Areas with a short dry season and at least 2,000 millimeters annual rainfall are targeted.

Dr. Veronique Schmit, IRRI plant breeder and project coordinator, sees a dual role for such a rice plant in the uplands. "In addition to providing food for subsistence farmers and their families, it could be planted on hedgerows or used as a cover crop to prevent soil movement and reduce erosion," she says.

Resource conservation is seldom a priority of farmers when it conflicts with their need for food. "Perennial rice

P. Cenias

could help reconcile these interests," says Dr. Schmit. "Additionally, perennial rice would actually require less labor."

Dr. Schmit and her team will also tailor the perennial rice plant they are designing to withstand common upland pressures from weeds, diseases (mainly blast), nematodes, and drought. Productivity should be 1-2 tons per hectare, comparable to that of traditional or improved cultivars.

The first 3-year phase of this long-term project, which began in 1995, is supported by the German Agency for Technical Cooperation.

To date, two suitable donors of the perennial trait have been identified in accessions *Oryza longistaminata* and *O. rufipogon*, both wild species. They are being screened to evaluate their perenniality and resistance to drought, and then crossed with upland cultivars to transfer their perenniality.

The breeding team has also found a high level of resistance to the nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola* in an *O. longistaminata* accession used in the crosses—an important breakthrough. "This nematode is the most damaging species in the upland ecosystem of Southeast Asia," Dr. Schmit says. "No good source of resistance was available before."

When do upland farmers use contour hedgerows?

Upland farmers with secure land tenure, access to markets, and/or land with steep slopes are more likely to adopt contour hedgerow technology than farmers under other conditions.

IRRI social scientists surveyed 130 upland farmers in Cebu and Claveria, Philippines, to try to understand why some farmers on sloping lands use contour hedgerows to control erosion while others do not.

"Market access allows farmers to respond to the demand for cash crops," says Dr. Sushil Pandey, IRRI agricultural economist, "and it increases the potential for cash cropping that can generate greater returns, which then allows farmers to invest in conservation practices."

Farmers with limited land area are less likely to adopt the technology because contour hedgerows can reduce the cultivable area by as much as 20 percent. Nonfarm income can help reduce the capital constraints to adoption of the technology.

Dr. Pandey explains that knowing how these socioeconomic factors affect the adoption process helps planners to target the technology and to design policy and institutional reforms aimed at increasing the rate of adoption. Implica-

tions gleaned from the study include the importance of information campaigns to convince farmers about the benefits of soil conservation and the role that improved rural infrastructure, marketing institutions, and tenure status may play in accelerating the adoption of conservation technology.

Consortium focuses on upland rice researchers

The Upland Rice Research Consortium (URRC), now in its seventh year, is providing an invaluable mechanism for bringing together upland rice researchers to solve problems in a difficult ecosystem.

Contour hedgerows controlling erosion in the uplands of Negros, Philippines.

“We believe that increasing the productivity of unfavorable rice ecosystems can be best achieved through partnerships between national and international scientists,” says Dr. Colin Piggin, program leader for upland rice ecosystem research.

The URRC is a collaborative network involving Brazil, India, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam—all countries with large areas of upland rice and strong upland rice

research programs. Bangladesh, China, and Myanmar are associate members. The Government of Germany is funding the URRC from 1997 to 1999. The Asian Development Bank funded it from 1991 to 1993, and the Governments of Germany and Japan from 1994 to 1996.

Many experiments are under way to improve scientists’ understanding of the major constraints in the uplands, especially nutrient availability, weeds, and drought. Some of the highlights follow.

URRC researchers who are studying nutrient availability are finding that farmers can use legume rotations to provide nitrogen and organic matter. Phosphorus must come from fertilizers, but its formulation can greatly influence its effectiveness. The biology of prolific weeds such as *Eleusine indica*, *Borreria laevis*, and *Ageratum conyzoides* is being studied in Indonesia and the Philippines where researchers are verifying that control efforts must start early in the season. Indian and IRRI researchers studying drought are finding that degree of leaf rolling, leaf drying, and root growth are important traits to consider when selecting rice lines for drought tolerance.

URRC researchers have been developing many breeding lines with resistance/tolerance to major upland constraints; these are being incorporated into national breeding programs. Scientists have also found that upland rice is very important in subsistence economies where population and market access are low—often in places where the world’s poorest people live.

In the future, URRC collaborators will continue to conduct research that tackles constraints associated with drought, nutrient availability, soil acidity, weeds, diseases, sustainability, crop management, socioeconomic conditions, technology adoption, and marketing. ■

Upland rice farmers in Lao PDR constantly struggle to keep ahead of weeds in their fields.

G. Heitel

Flood-prone rice

AROUND 12.8 MILLION hectares of ricelands worldwide are subject to uncontrolled flooding—nearly 89 percent of this area is confined to South and Southeast Asia. Rice yields are low and extremely variable because of problem soils and unpredictable combinations of drought and flood. There are three major kinds of flood-prone rice: deepwater, which tolerates water depths of 50-100 centimeters, floating, which can be found in water up to 400 centimeters deep, and tidal wetland, which can survive submergence, sometimes in salty water, for short periods.

D. Puckridge

Shrimp pose salty question in Bangladesh

Shrimp and rice seem to be the perfect enterprise for making farmers rich in Bangladesh's low-lying, saline coastal areas. Or is it?

Concerns are rising that these entrepreneurs may be sacrificing long-term environmental stability for quick money.

"Many people believe that shrimp farming is increasing salinity and other toxic buildups in the soil, which will eventually harm both rice and shrimp production," explains Dr. Mahabub Hossain, economist and head of IRRI's Social Sciences Division. "Others are concerned about short-term investors disrupting the delicate social equilibrium in these rural areas."

IRRI social scientists and their partners from the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute decided to study these very real concerns before the fragile lands are irreparably damaged and the livelihoods of the millions of people who depend on them destroyed.

To get the big picture, researchers surveyed 41 villages plus 570 farm

households in Khulna District, where this new enterprise is really taking off.

Most of the farmers in the district own less than 0.6 hectare. They usually grow traditional rice cultivars during the monsoon season because modern high-yielding rice often cannot tolerate the salinity. In the dry season, most of the lands are left fallow, and profits from rice are typically low. But shrimp farming is quickly changing that.

"The new rice-shrimp farming system is gaining popularity in the saline areas because of the high profits," explains Dr. Hossain. "Growers earn about US\$1,130 per hectare from raising rice and shrimp—or about three times more than from rice alone."

The easy money has captured the imagination of small farmers and big land owners alike—as well as that of outside entrepreneurs.

And this is precisely the concern.

Currently, only one-fifth of the land in the district is used for raising shrimp. But more than half the farmers interviewed report increasing salinity from shrimp operations, raising the question: what will happen to the environment if more people start raising shrimp?

"Shorter duration rice varieties and improved management techniques for

both rice and shrimp are needed to protect the environment as the area under rice-shrimp culture expands," advises Dr. Hossain. "The critical issue is to determine how to ensure the sustainability of this profitable enterprise—which requires more research."

Big yields from "smart" deepwater rice

Deepwater rice is notorious for its amazing ability to elongate its stems—and for its inability to produce much grain.

Until now.

IRRI scientists and their collaborators have created modern deepwater rice lines that can produce the same amount of grain as irrigated rice—while thriving in water up to 1 meter deep.

"The key is in the structure of the stems and leaves, called the canopy, that floats above the water," explains Dr. Dharmawansa Senadhira, IRRI plant breeder and program leader for flood-prone rice ecosystem research. "If the canopy of deepwater rice is short and erect—like the canopy of irrigated rice—both rice types will produce about the same amount of grain when grown under the same weather conditions using 80 kilograms of nitrogen per hectare."

Thousands of farmers and their families in Thailand depend on deepwater rice for their livelihoods.

When nine promising deepwater rice lines were tested at IRRI, the six with short, erect canopy structures above the water produced an average of nearly 5 tons of grain per hectare. The three with tall canopies yielded only 2.5 tons per hectare, and the three modern irrigated rice cultivars planted in the adjacent plot averaged 4.7 tons per hectare. Traditional deepwater rice varieties usually produce only 1 ton per hectare.

In years when the flooding is not so severe—an increasingly common phenomenon—and the waters are only 30-40 centimeters deep, these new plant types will look and perform like very high-yielding rice varieties.

“They know—unlike the traditional varieties—how much to elongate and how to keep their canopies above the water,” explains Dr. Senadhira.

Farmers are already testing some of the new deepwater rice types developed in Thailand in their fields. Dr. Senadhira is optimistic that, in the not too distant future, these new plant types may be transforming these deepwater areas into more productive lands.

Rice varieties boost yields and improve saline soils

A research partnership linking scientists in India, the United Kingdom (UK), and the Philippines is bringing a previously rare product to poor farmers: rice varieties that tolerate saline stresses and help to improve deteriorated soils.

One of these varieties is CSR10, which was developed by the Central Soil Salinity Research Institute (CSSRI) in Karnal, India, and released in 1989. And nine new saline-tolerant varieties—CSR21 through CSR29—will soon be released to Indian farmers, the direct result of a productive, long-term partnership.

The term “saline” includes both salt (coastal and inland) and alkaline stresses. “Combined, these twin stresses are regarded as the largest soil toxicity problem facing rice production—8.5 million hectares in India alone,” says Dr. B. Mishra, principal rice breeder and head of CSSRI’s Crop Improvement Division.

Developing tolerant varieties has been painstakingly slow. “Early collaborative work in the 1970s involving the University of Sussex and IRRI demonstrated that tolerance is not a single character, but a complex and quantitative trait,” says Dr. Tony Yeo, a plant physiologist at Sussex. The UK’s Department for International Development (DFID), previously called the Overseas Development Administration (ODA) has continuously supported the work.

It took CSSRI breeders 18 years to overcome this complexity and develop CSR10. “But what a variety it is,” says Dr. Mishra. “Emanating from salinity-tolerant traditional varieties, CSR10 was the first high-yielding, early-maturing variety for saline soils in India.”

Under highly deteriorated salt-affected soils, CSR10 yields 3.0-4.5 tons per hectare; under moderate stress, it yields up to 5.5 tons per hectare. When CSR10 is grown year after year, it actually enhances productivity by improving highly deteriorated alkaline soils without amendments.

Dr. Mishra is optimistic that the soon-to-be released varieties will do the same: “This ‘biological’ management of saline-affected soils is a major boon to resource-poor farmers who cannot afford chemical soil amendments.”

On moderately saline or alkaline soils, the yield potential of the new varieties is even higher than that of CSR10. They may be grown in coastal and tidal areas or in inland saline areas under irrigated or rainfed lowland conditions.

The varieties were derived from advanced breeding lines developed at IRRI and screened at CSSRI and 11 salinity tolerance sites across India. DFID support has enhanced the CSSRI-IRRI collaboration since 1996.

“This effort shows the worth of an international shuttle breeding approach,” says IRRI’s Dr. Senadhira. A similar DFID-supported shuttle project has resulted in the recent release of two salt-tolerant rice varieties in the Philippines. ■

New saline-tolerant rice varieties are being developed through collaborative work at the Central Soil Salinity Research Institute in Karnal, India.

G. Heitel

Cross-ecosystems

Earth-friendly system for transforming rice

A common soil bacterium is helping scientists transform rice with new genes—safely and economically.

Called *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation, the system is one of three that IRRI scientists are using for inserting new genes—such as for insect, bacterial, or fungal resistance, and submergence and salinity tolerance—into rice.

“Compared with the protoplast and biolistic transformation systems, the *Agrobacterium*-mediated transfer system is easier, safer, more efficient—and a lot cheaper to use,” explains Dr. Swapan Datta, IRRI tissue culture specialist.

Agrobacterium tumefaciens is a naturally occurring bacterium that causes galls to form in dicots, such as tobacco. Once the galls form, the bacteria inhabit them. But galls normally do not form on monocots, such as grasses and lilies.

Scientists have long used this bacterium as a vector to successfully transfer foreign genes into dicots. To transform plants, new genes are cloned into plasmids (a DNA molecule harbored within a host cell that replicates independently of the host chromosome) that are subsequently introduced into modified *A. tumefaciens*.

The tricky part has been to get monocots to host the bacterium. Researchers at IRRI and elsewhere have succeeded in coaxing several of them to do this, including rice.

“The system is primarily for use with rice cultivars that are highly responsive in tissue culture,” explains Dr. Karabi Datta, tissue culture specialist.

The Dattas and their team have developed a protocol for the transformation of several rice cultivars with genes aiming for tolerance for salinity, and

R. Cabrera

Despite widespread adoption of modern rice varieties, poverty remains a problem in rural Bangladesh.

Using a common soil bacterium, scientists are perfecting a transformation system for inserting new genes into rice—safely and economically.

R. Cabrera

resistance to stem borer, sheath blight, and bacterial leaf blight.

Scientists from Japan provided the *Agrobacterium* strain for this work.

A workshop on the new technique was held in April 1997 to train scientists from national agricultural research systems (NARS) on its use through the Asian Rice Biotechnology Network (ARBN). Some of these scientists are now testing the system in their own research programs.

Initiated in 1993 with grants from the Asian Development Bank and the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation, the ARBN has the goal of ensuring that the benefits of biotechnology reach NARS scientists. The Rockefeller Foundation provides additional support. Members are the NARS of China, India, Indonesia, Pakistan, Philippines, Republic of Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam; Bangladesh and Sri Lanka are associate members.

Cold rice, hot rice— why the yield gap?

Top irrigated rice yields of more than 15 tons per hectare have been recorded in temperate areas. But in the tropical lowlands, yields have peaked out at only 10 tons per hectare.

Why the difference?

A longer growth duration in the cooler temperate areas is commonly believed to be the reason for the greater yield potential. But the factors within the plant that are responsible for the difference have eluded researchers for years.

In a collaborative effort, scientists from Yunnan Academy of Agricultural Sciences and IRRI decided to try to solve the mystery by growing several high-yielding rice varieties in 1995 and 1996 in a temperate area (Taoyuan Township, Yunnan, China) and the tropics (IRRI headquarters in the Philippines).

Shanyou 63, a Chinese hybrid, produced an amazing 15.2 tons per hectare at Yunnan, but its average yield at IRRI was only 8.6 tons per hectare. Tropical rice cultivars performed similarly, producing, on average, 12.8 tons per hectare at Yunnan and 8.5 tons per hectare

at IRRI. Scientists pinpointed two factors that seem responsible for this yield difference: the number of spikelets (the grain-bearing structures) and the biomass (the total plant material produced).

Across genotypes, Yunnan-grown rice produced an average 33 percent more grain in 1995 and 62 percent more in 1996 than the same rice grown at IRRI. Biomass production was 42 percent more at Yunnan than at IRRI in 1995 and 58 percent more in 1996.

More spikelets and biomass increase the daily crop growth rate, which was significantly more at Yunnan than at IRRI during the vegetative and grain-filling stages. Greater leaf area index and lower respiration—due to lower night temperatures—also increase the rate.

“Further improvement in tropical rice yield potential will depend on scientists’ ability to increase spikelet numbers per unit ground area and the biomass produced,” explains Dr. Shaobing Peng, IRRI associate crop physiologist.

Scientists from IRRI, NARS, and advanced laboratories are working to modify the current plant type to have more spikelets and to increase biomass by improving crop photosynthesis and reducing respiration losses.

Poverty in Bangladesh lessens—but too slowly

Has poverty been decreasing in Bangladesh? Has agricultural growth stagnated? Have modern rice varieties made farmers better off?

To answer these questions, IRRI scientists teamed up with researchers from the Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies to quantify the changes in the rural economy. The first survey of 20 households in each of 62 villages across the country was done in 1987; the same households were revisited in 1995.

“Poverty in rural Bangladesh was reduced from 60 to 52 percent of the people between 1987 and 1994,” says Dr. Mahabub Hossain, economist and head of IRRI’s Social Sciences Division.

The Bangladesh rural economy, which supports 80 percent of the population and contributes 72 percent of the national income, made satisfactory progress during the period because of rapid growth in rural nonfarm activities.

“But agricultural growth slowed drastically,” Dr. Hossain says. Nonfarm activities, such as trade and transport, comprised 46 percent of rural income in 1994, up from 37 percent in 1987. Labor has also been leaving agriculture for more lucrative nonfarm work, and the agricultural sector has become more efficient—further displacing labor.

“Expanded irrigation systems, reduced population growth, improved rural infrastructure, and rapid rural-urban migration contributed the most to productivity growth,” Dr. Hossain says.

The combination of irrigation and modern high-yielding rice varieties dramatically influenced income, with yields increasing from 2.4 to 3.2 tons per hectare. The area irrigated using modern technologies increased from 21 to 42 percent, and the area covered by modern varieties increased from 31 to 65 percent between the surveys. The effect on household income, however, was less dramatic because of lower rice prices and higher labor costs.

The average household income of US\$220 per annum, however, continued to be distributed unequally. In 1994 the top 10 percent of the households controlled half the land and 32 percent of the income; the bottom 40 percent owned 2 percent of the land and earned only 16 percent of the income.

The outlook for the country, however, remains sobering. “Poverty is still more prevalent in Bangladesh than in its neighbors,” says Dr. Hossain. “Few resources are unexploited, and many available technologies have already been adopted. Economic growth from the nonfarm sector must be accelerated if poverty is to be alleviated within an acceptable time horizon.” ■

Conserving and promoting genetic diversity

Conserving the rice world's biodiversity

Germplasm specialists from IRRI, in partnership with scientists from national programs, are journeying to more than 20 countries in Asia and Africa in a race against time to collect and preserve traditional rice varieties and wild rice species before they vanish from the earth.

Since 1994, through a 5-year project sponsored by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), IRRI has supported partner countries in collecting and conserving rice genetic resources and strengthening germplasm conservation at the national level. The three components of the project involve field collection of germplasm, on-farm conservation (see IRRI's 1995-96 Corporate Report, *Listening to the farmers*, pp 60-62), and national staff training and genebank facility development.

As more and more improved rice varieties make their way into farmers' fields, low-yielding traditional varieties and land races of the two cultivated *Oryza* species are being abandoned. Alarming genetic erosion is also occurring in the 22 wild *Oryza* species as fragile habitats deteriorate with changes in the environment, particularly in countries undergoing rapid economic development.

"We stand to lose irreplaceable genetic resources contained in these two gene pools," says Dr. Bao-Rong Lu, germplasm specialist in the IRRI Genetic Resources Center.

The SDC-sponsored project is well on track to preventing this catastrophe. In 1995 and 1996 alone, 4,884 previously uncollected seed samples of unique

B. LU

populations (4,481 cultivated, 403 wild) were rescued from oblivion. More than 3,800 duplicate backup samples now reside in the International Rice Genebank at IRRI headquarters. About half the accessions came from Lao PDR, which has large areas previously unvisited by rice germplasm collectors. Other partner countries in which collection and/or training activities are being funded in 1997 are Bangladesh, Bhutan, Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Madagascar, Malaysia, Mozambique, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, and Vietnam.

Working with national agricultural extension workers and outreach scientific staff is the most practical scenario for collecting germplasm. "Extension workers know their areas—and the farmers—very well," says Ms. Genoveva Loresto, IRRI germplasm specialist. "Unfortunately, extension workers and even local plant genetic resources workers are often poorly trained or not trained at all in collecting crop germplasm. The SDC Project is

meeting a pressing need to train these people so they can assist in field collection." In 1996, in-country training on collection activities was provided for 200 national extension and plant genetic resources workers in seven countries.

Participating countries will ultimately control their own base collections of all the traditional varieties, land races, and wild species collected locally. Some countries are already preserving their local germplasm in their own genebanks staffed by well-trained professionals—and other countries will soon be able to, thanks to the SDC Project.

Matching rice varieties with environments

Scientists are now using new, powerful computer tools to improve their understanding of interactions between rice genotypes and the environments in which they are grown.

Researchers with the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice

Wild rice species, such as this population in Bangladesh, must be collected and preserved before they vanish completely.

(INGER), in collaboration with IRRI's Biometrics Unit, are using additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) biometrical models and pattern analysis to analyze and interpret data from five 1996 INGER yield and observational trials in the irrigated and rainfed lowland ecosystems. The results are being used to classify the test locations based on varietal reactions to the test environments; 1997 data will be used to verify them.

"We cluster the test locations and genotypes according to similarities and differences in varietal response, and then look for site characteristics leading to these interactions," says Dr. Graham McLaren, head of IRRI's Biometrics Unit. "This allows us to identify germplasm with specific adaptation to environment groups and particular conditions, which will be useful in readjusting test sites for rationalized INGER operations."

During 1996, training sessions were held at IRRI headquarters and in several

countries to share the new methods of analyzing and interpreting multilocation trials. With these new skills and computer software provided by IRRI, national system scientists from Bangladesh, China, India, Indonesia, Philippines, and Thailand can now analyze and interpret genotype by environment interaction using multisite data.

Multisite evaluation since 1975 has produced a wealth of data. "Analysis of interaction in these data will generate valuable base information that will help us match the right rice varieties with the right environments," says Dr. Ram Chaudhary, INGER coordinator.

Two important germplasm databases now on-line

A wealth of information on rice genetic resources is now accessible through two computerized databases: the International Rice Genebank Collection Information System (IRGCIS), IRRI's in-house database, and the System-wide Information Network for Genetic Resources (SINGER) on the World Wide Web.

Developing the IRGCIS has been one of the most important elements of upgrading the operations and procedures of the International Rice Genebank, which began in 1993 and was completed in May 1997.

"Access to data on more than 81,000 accessions in the IRRI collection across all genebank operations is needed on a daily basis," says Dr. Michael Jackson, head of the Genetic Resources Center.

Through the IRGCIS, International Rice Genebank staff members and IRRI researchers can access germplasm data directly through the Institute's local area network. Links with the SINGER database accelerated the migration of the IRGCIS to a Windows platform. "The logistics of this migration would not have

been possible without support from the SINGER Project," says Dr. Jackson.

Funded by the SDC and the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency, the SINGER Project is an outstanding example of collaboration among centers of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). It is promoted by the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute-managed System-wide Genetic Resources Program. IRRI has actively participated in SINGER from its inception, according to data management specialists Adel Alcantara and Vanji Guevarra. "In fact," says Ms. Alcantara, "data from the IRRI system were used in a prototype version of SINGER to demonstrate its feasibility."

Only a few years ago, a project as complex as SINGER could not have been carried out in the same way. The demand for cross-center information on the germplasm collections maintained by IRRI and 11 other centers materialized at the same time that computer technology evolved to permit such an initiative.

"At IRRI, we can feed data into the SINGER database yet still retain our database independence," Dr. Jackson says. "That's a very big bonus for us, given the amount of work we carried out to develop the IRGCIS."

Through the World Wide Web at <<http://noc1.cgiar.org>> and since the end of May 1997 on CD-ROM, researchers worldwide have access to information about the CGIAR germplasm collections, their status, and how they are being used.

In terms of fulfilling the CGIAR center responsibilities under the agreements with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) signed in 1994, and the wider concerns about germplasm access and exchange that have emerged in several international forums, the SINGER Project has demonstrated its value in increasing transparency about the management of these important germplasm collections. ■

Information and knowledge exchange

Rice, rice, rice on the WWW

Promising "everything you want to know about the world's longest running cereal," IRRI's first electronic publication has become the World Wide Web's hub for rice information.

"We are really excited about Riceweb, which is an expanded version of the popular paper publication *The Rice Almanac*," says Mr. Gene Hettel, head of IRRI's Communication and Publications Services.

Found on the World Wide Web at <<http://www.riceweb.org>>, Riceweb—originally launched by IRRI—is a collaborative effort with the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical and the West Africa Rice Development Association. Spanish and French versions of selected sections are being planned for clients in Latin America and West Africa.

Riceweb features basic educational information on rice, including geography of rice production, links to databases, a glossary of 3,000 rice terms, and even rice recipes—including how to make saki.

Four organizations have identified Riceweb as an outstanding educational science site for both children and adults: *The New Scientist*, Net Scout Report, Bonus.Com, and Biology Net.

"The ultimate goal is to link all rice-related sites under one web address," says Ms. Carolyn Dedolph, IRRI science editor and writer.

IRRI Library: global impact

Rice scientists around the world are increasingly discovering the rich resources of the IRRI Library.

"Researchers are finding out about our Web Catalog—called the WebCat—

M. Wenceslao

and asking for more information," says Mr. Ian Wallace, IRRI librarian. "We have extended our reach to countries where we were not very well known before: Pakistan, Mozambique, and Brazil, for example."

The WebCat offers many possibilities to international clients. Scientists can read electronic journals, visit the web sites of other organizations, connect to the world's greatest libraries, or even read a daily newspaper from Jakarta, Madras, or Tokyo.

"Rice scientists are closer than ever before to the information they need," Mr. Wallace says.

Public awareness efforts target diverse media

Increased and improved public awareness (PA)—including greater focus on collaborative activities with donors and research partners—resulted in an excellent evaluation by an external panel of journalists in an audit of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research Centers' PA programs.

One measurable impact of the PA effort is the increased diversity of the types of media that featured the Insti-

tute in 1996-97: international print and broadcast news, in-flight magazines of major airlines, bank and commodities newsletters, and popular science magazines. Positive headlines, such as "We cannot afford to lose IRRI" in the *Bangkok Post*, were common.

Scientific publishing enters new era

IRRI's scientific publishing program continues to produce high quality materials for the world's rice researchers.

The Institute published nine books in 1996, either independently or as dual imprints with major science publishing houses in Europe and Asia. Three issues of the *International rice research notes* and eight titles in the *IRRI discussion paper series* were also produced and distributed.

New information delivery techniques, such as the World Wide Web and CD-ROM technology, are being explored to speed up the exchange of scientific information. Already, abstracts and some full papers are available on the IRRI home page.

"We are currently surveying our clients to ensure that information is

s from the world of rice

R. Cabrera

The Riceweb has become the hub for rice information on the World Wide Web.

IRRI's 1996-1997 Corporate Report, *Listening to the farmers*, won four major awards in an international competition.

The Riceworld web site enables visitors to take a tour of the world's only museum dedicated to rice—without having to travel to the Philippines.

R. Cabrera

to “tour” the museum from anywhere in the world.

The Riceworld home page focuses on the nonscience side of rice, including exhibits on rice-based cultures, rice artifacts, rice’s influence on societies, and a rice teaser game.

Listening to the farmers receives major awards

At its 1997 international meeting in Cleveland, Ohio, the US-based Agricultural Communicators in Education presented four awards to the team of writers, editors, designers, and photographers responsible for IRRRI’s 1995-1996 Corporate Report, *Listening to the farmers*.

An Outstanding Professional Skill Award, two Gold Awards for the overall publication and graphic design, and a Silver Award for the cover recognized this team effort that put names and faces on IRRRI’s ultimate partners—the farmers. ■

being disseminated through the most appropriate and desired channels,” Mr. Hettel says.

Riceworld visitors up; WWW provides access

The IRRRI Riceworld continues to draw record-breaking numbers of visitors. More than 87,000 people from 53 countries toured the museum in 1996—nearly double 1995’s 48,000, with Filipino school children comprising the majority.

“We are thrilled that IRRRI Riceworld is such a success,” says Mr. Mar Movillon, manager of IRRRI’s Visitors, Exhibition and Conference Services. “In the coming years, we plan to attract even more visitors as we update and improve our exhibits.”

The IRRRI Riceworld now has even more of a global reach with the launching of its home page on the World Wide Web <<http://www.riceworld.org>>. The site provides an opportunity for people

Training

Training accelerates the impact of rice science

IRRI welcomed its first group of 37 trainees more than 35 years ago. Since then, 7,800 scientists from 96 countries have come to IRRI headquarters for research fellowships or degree, nondegree, and group training.

A 1996 mail survey of 612 past IRRI degree scholars and 1,727 former trainees, conducted by postdoctoral researcher Dr. Khan Rana from Pakistan, helped to substantiate the tangible benefits derived from donor investments in human resources developed through IRRI's training program. Interviews of training alumni conducted by Ms. Ruby R.V. Cruz, a Ph D scholar from Pangasinan State University, Philippines, also provided information.

"Our goal was to document results," says Dr. Robert T. Raab, acting head of IRRI's Training Center. "We looked specifically at the impact of training on advancing rice science, disseminating technology, and developing national rice research systems."

Advancing rice science. More than 120 former degree scholars responded they were able to introduce specific innovations or make changes in their research as a result of their training; 131 indicated that their training was instrumental in helping them initiate related research studies at their home institutions, apply research methodologies, and diagnose and focus on priority problems. Respondents also said that IRRI training increased their ability to prepare quality scientific papers.

Dr. Behzad Ghareyazie, an Iranian scientist who specializes in rice transformation, is one of IRRI's training success stories.

Contributing to the body of knowledge. Almost 1,200 scientists have conducted their MS and/or Ph D thesis research under the supervision of IRRI scientists. "It is important to assess the significant contributions that some of these studies have made to furthering scientific knowledge and the resulting practical applications," asserts Dr. Raab.

Three examples especially stand out:

- Dr. Vichien Petpisit from Thailand studied the inheritance of bacterial blight resistance in rice. In 1974, he identified two new resistance genes—*Xa4* and *xa5*. Since then, these genes have been used in numerous developing country breeding programs. Many bacterial blight-resistant rice varieties now have one of these two genes.
- In 1975, Indian scientist Dr. Ammala Lakshminarayana studied the inheritance of brown planthopper (BPH) resistance in rice. He identified two new genes—*Bph3* and *bph4*—that

are still used extensively in developing high-yielding varieties with BPH resistance.

- Dr. Behzad Ghareyazie, from Iran, completed in 1996 his study on transformation of indica and other rice types related to genetic integration, expression, and inheritance of enhanced insect resistance. The transgenic rice obtained as a result of his work expressed the *Bacillus thuringiensis* gene, which provides a high level of stem borer resistance. It is proving to be particularly useful in Dr. Ghareyazie's home country and is also being used in breeding programs throughout Asia.

Disseminating technology. The main goal of several of IRRI's group training courses is technology dissemination, such as courses on biotechnology under the auspices of the Asian Rice Biotechnology Network (ARBN). Many survey respondents gave credit to their IRRI training for helping them find better

ways to do things. Examples include the adoption of IRRI screening and breeding methodologies, improved seed processing, multilocation testing, genetic resource conservation, insect rearing, experimental procedures, and research program formulation.

Developing national rice research systems. To understand the impact of training on national systems, the researchers focused on Cambodia, where IRRI has, since 1987, embarked on a major program of human resource development and technical assistance through the Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP). The Project's own training team was trained first. Its members then became responsible for conducting in-country technical rice training, developing new courses, and creating and translating training materials. So far, the CIAP training team has conducted 71 in-country training courses involving 1,900 participants, supervised the thesis research of 25 degree students, and spon-

M. Quiamco

sored intensive English language training. In addition, several Cambodian scientists have gone to IRRI headquarters or Thailand for CIAP-sponsored non-degree short courses or have participated in study tours and international conferences.

"Because of these substantial investments in training over the past 10 years, Cambodia has greatly increased its capacity to plan and execute a national rice research and development program," says Dr. Glenn Denning, head of IRRI's International Programs Management Office.

Recent achievements directly resulting from IRRI's training activities include

- Release of three traditional medium-duration varieties, all of which are pureline selections from traditional Cambodian varieties.
- Identification of significant new pests (grasshoppers, ants, rice aphids, and golden apple snails).
- Completion of replicated trials across 25 locations to examine fertilizer response of rice.
- Research on labor-intensive land preparation, land leveling and water management, and crop establishment.

Future training challenges. The years ahead pose a challenge for IRRI's training program as the rice research agenda becomes more complex and

Members of the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium have benefited from training courses created to specifically address their research needs.

funding for training activities becomes more scarce.

"Nevertheless," says Dr. Raab, "IRRI will continue its work to accelerate the impact of rice research by developing the capabilities of NARS rice scientists."

Accomplishments in 1996

- Extended degree and postdegree training to 162 scientists from 23 countries.
- Eighty-five scholars and fellows, mostly from Asia and the Pacific, completed their programs.
- Conducted eight group courses at IRRI headquarters for 100 NARS scientists from 22 countries.
- Developed 15 instructional aids (manuals, guidebooks, videos) that document the technical content of eight group training courses.
- Conducted seven national courses, providing 338 scientists with opportunities to update their skills. ■

R. Cabrera

Strengthening international partnerships

Accelerating progress in selected national research systems through country- and ecosystem-specific support programs and networks requires a strong commitment from the partners involved.

“By increasing research capacity of our national system partners, we are fostering closer working relationships that will ultimately benefit rice farmers and consumers,” says Dr. Glenn Denning, head of IRRI’s International Programs Management Office.

Activities of the Crop and Resource Management Network (CREMNET) are an integral part of this program. The Network’s goal is to facilitate the free exchange, participatory evaluation, and promotion of promising crop and resource management technologies for higher and sustainable productivity of rice-based cropping systems. Highlighted are CREMNET’s evaluation of direct wet seeding techniques as alternatives to labor-intensive transplanting and activities in selected partner countries.

Evaluating direct wet seeding techniques

“Wet seeding is becoming increasingly popular in Asia,” says Dr. Vethaiya Balasubramanian, CREMNET coordinator. “This is because of increasing labor costs and the availability of cheap, effective herbicides and suitable varieties.”

CREMNET collaborators are evaluating two types of wet seeding: surface (aerobic) and subsurface (anaerobic). In surface seeding, pregerminated seeds are sown on well-puddled soil 1 or 2 days after the last puddling and leveling. The seeds are broadcast uniformly by hand or motorized sprayer. Alternately, a drum seeder may be used to sow seeds in rows. Surface-sown seeds, however,

L. Sayo

Direct wet seeding of rice is taking off in Asia as labor costs increase and effective herbicides and suitable varieties become available.

are vulnerable to damage by birds, rats, snails, torrential rains, and dry weather.

In subsurface seeding, pregerminated seeds are broadcast immediately after puddling and the suspended mud settles down to form a thin protective cover over the seeds. The seeds may also be sown in rows with an anaerobic seeder within 2 days of puddling.

CREMNET’s evaluation of these techniques is revealing that good land preparation and leveling (see related story, p 33) as well as high quality seeds, are vital to successful wet seeding. For both surface and subsurface methods, water management is critical for the first 10 days when the soil must be kept saturated but not flooded to facilitate seedling emergence and early growth.

According to Dr. Balasubramanian, CREMNET is assisting Indian, Philippine, and Myanmar farmers in evaluating and adapting drum and anaerobic seeders. “Farmers are telling us that row-seeded crops tend to require fewer seeds and are easier to weed and fertilize,” he says.

Madagascar and Mozambique

Rice is grown and consumed in most countries in Eastern, Central, and Southern Africa. Imports meet a third of this demand. Yet great potential exists for increasing regional production, particularly in Madagascar and Mozambique. Accomplishments in 1996-97 include

Trebuil

- Institutionalizing the shuttle breeding strategy in Madagascar. Scientists at three centers are becoming capable in specific types of screening: cold tolerance and iron toxicity tolerance at Mahitsy/Belanitra, rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) resistance plus cold tolerance and blast resistance at Lac Alaotra, and RYMV resistance at Tsararano.
- Continuing work to establish a national rice breeding program in Madagascar, supporting the country's regional research strategy, and promoting appropriate agricultural machinery and equipment (see feature story, pp 10-13).
- Completing three greenhouses at Madagascar's Tsararano Research Station, which will play a key role in the RYMV screening program.
- Proposing a project in Mozambique that aims to improve rice productivity in rainfed coastal areas with a long-term view of generating surpluses for export to South Africa and other countries in the region.

Cambodia

Cambodia produced a record 3.6 million tons of rice over the past year, according to its Ministry of Agriculture. The country's Undersecretary of State for Agriculture attributed the 160,000-ton surplus to research. Other accomplishments in 1996-97 include

- Starting the new phase of the Australia-supported Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP).
- Approving the release (by the Varietal Recommendations Committee of Cambodia) of three traditional late-duration varieties (CAR 7, CAR 8, and CAR 9) for the rainfed lowland ecosystem. Their yields were at least 20 percent higher than the check, Toul Samrong 2.

Bhutan

Agricultural research in Bhutan has come a long way since the early 1980s when there was virtually no structure to carry out projects in this isolated mountain kingdom. Starting in 1984, an IRRI project supported by the International

Development Research Centre showed the potential for rice yield increases through new varieties, improved soil fertility, and better weed control methods.

Since a third phase began in April 1995 with additional support coming from the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation, researchers have been focusing on renewable natural resource management (RNRM) that emphasizes farmer participation in sustaining productivity increases in Bhutan's wetland production system.

In May 1996, 25 RNRM staff were trained in participatory rural appraisal as a tool for diagnosing and providing solutions for Bhutan's RNRM problems—using farmer participation as a key element. The Project has contributed enormously to building human resources and research capacity in the country. ■

Strong research partnerships are the key to helping countries, such as Vietnam, improve their rice production practices.

Finance and administration

Staff restructuring program completed

In the last quarter of 1996, IRRI Management addressed a budget crisis brought about by funding shortfalls. The deficit—almost US\$2 million that unfolded in the middle of 1996 and more than US\$6 million in 1997—stemmed from the inability of several major donors to maintain previous funding levels.

Major cost-cutting was implemented, including a staff restructuring program (SRP) in which 621 positions were eliminated (598 national, 15 international, and 8 affiliate).

Nationally recruited employees who left IRRI under the SRP received a generous package, comparable to those offered by multinational corporations in the country, and higher than the Philippine Labor Code's mandatory provisions. In addition to the financial package, an assistance program was set up to help separated employees find work elsewhere. Several groups of separated employees have formed corporations and are now providing IRRI with services.

The SRP, which was a very complex and sensitive activity with considerable legal, political, and labor implications, was completed in early February 1997.

"With reduced operational costs as a result of overall staff reduction, plus the efficiencies we have effected in our service areas, we should end 1997 in a much better position," says IRRI Director General George Rothschild.

Partnership: essence of the new medium-term plan

The Institute completed a Medium-term Plan (MTP) that will guide its research activities from 1998 through 2000. The MTP theme, *Sustaining food security beyond the year 2000: A global partnership for rice research*, reinforces the impor-

tance IRRI places on the key role of partnerships—as does this corporate report. With the growing complexity of problems that rice research must address, IRRI acknowledges that it cannot tackle these problems alone.

With the commitment given by NARS to take over some of IRRI's previous research agenda, the Institute hopes to pursue more effectively new opportunities for upstream research, such as applying biotechnology to address problems in unfavorable rice-growing areas.

IRRI staff members earn awards

Present and past IRRI rice breeders, Dr. Gurdev S. Khush and Mr. Henry M. Beachell, shared the 1996 World Food Prize. The award recognizes the achievements of individuals who have advanced human development by improving the quality, quantity, or availability of food in the world.

During Dr. Khush's tenure over the past 29 years as the Institute's principal plant breeder, national rice improvement programs throughout the world have released more than 300 new rice varieties derived from materials and progeny developed by his breeding team.

Mr. Beachell, who retired as head of IRRI's Plant Breeding Department in 1972, led the team of scientists who developed IR8, the world's first high-yielding rice variety.

Other IRRI staff recognized included

- Ms. Thelma R. Paris, senior associate scientist, the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research's (CGIAR) Outstanding Local Professional Award for her work on linking human nutrition and agriculture.
- Dr. Shaobing Peng, associate crop physiologist, the CGIAR's Promising Young Scientist Award for his work on characterizing the physiological processes underlying yield potential in rice.
- Mr. Ramiro Cabrera, manager of IRRI's Creative and Production Ser-

vices, the International Award of Excellence presented by the Agricultural Communicators in Education for his lifetime contributions and achievements in international agriculture.

International Rice Award for the King of Thailand

In recognition of His Majesty's contributions to rice research and development during his 50-year reign, IRRI bestowed an International Rice Award on His Majesty King Bhumibol Adulyadej of Thailand. The historic event in the Grand Palace on 5 June 1996 was attended by an IRRI delegation headed by Board Chairman Dr. Roelof Rabbinge.

This first and only award ever given by IRRI to an individual recognizes His Majesty's passionate and personal devotion to improving the well-being of rice farmers and consumers, and his tireless efforts in putting the interests of the Thai people foremost in his 50 years on the throne.

IRRI's financial statements in separate booklet

IRRI's audited financial statements, which provide detailed information on the Institute's financial circumstances, are published in a separate booklet. It is automatically sent along with this Corporate Report only to donors and others who require detailed financial information in addition to the certified audited statements sent directly by the Director for Finance.

Additional certified copies are available on request from the Office of the Director for Finance.

The table on the facing page provides information on support from IRRI donors in 1996. Partner institutions collaborating with IRRI are listed on pp 53-54. Ongoing IRRI complementary projects are listed on IRRI's home page <<http://www.cgiar.org/irri>>. ■

Summary of financial support to IRRI agenda and nonagenda projects committed for 1996.

Source	Amount (US\$)			
	Agenda		Nonagenda projects	Total
	Unrestricted	Restricted		
Japan	5,151,190	3,344,276	626,250	9,121,716
World Bank	4,800,000 ^a			4,800,000
United States Agency for International Development	2,900,000		642,860	3,542,860
Denmark	2,065,339 ^a		322	2,065,661
Canadian International Development Agency	765,529			765,529
Swedish Agency for Research Cooperation	715,754			715,754
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation/German Agency for Technical Coop.		825,465	544,510	1,369,975
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation, Germany	711,783			711,783
European Union		1,500,000		1,500,000
Department for International Development (formerly ODA), United Kingdom		1,254,160	219,896	1,474,056
United Nations Development Programme		968,230	697,027	1,665,257
Australia	669,150	29,134	732,028	1,430,312
The Rockefeller Foundation		314,556	683,835	998,391
France ^b		347,127		347,127
Switzerland		309,244	3,157,070	3,466,314
Korea, Republic of	200,000	30,000	116,342	346,342
Philippines	209,162			209,162
The Netherlands	181,991		71,371	253,362
Norway	154,655			154,655
India		150,000		150,000
Belgium	96,327		116,733	213,060
People's Republic of China	90,000			90,000
Spain	40,000			40,000
Indonesia	12,500			12,500
Asian Development Bank			1,008,000	1,008,000
Environmental Protection Agency, United States of America			361,505	361,505
International Development Research Centre, Canada			211,833	211,833
Islamic Republic of Iran			179,862	179,862
Others			265,555	265,555
Total	18,763,380	9,072,192	9,634,999	37,470,571

^a Includes one-time payment toward 1996 shortfunding: World Bank (US\$600,000) and Denmark (US\$1,217,537). ^b The Government of France (through the research organizations CIRAD and ORSTOM) also provided IRRI the services of resident scientists. The value of their services cannot be quantified.

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PETER WHITE, *Ph D*, *soil scientist*

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Entomology and Plant Pathology

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TIM CHANCELLOR, *Ph D*, *affiliate scientist*
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BART COTTYN, *BS*, *project scientist*
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 REINER WASSMANN, *Ph D, IRS seconded from Fraunhofer Institute for Atmospheric Environmental Research*

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 ARNOLD R. MANZA, *MS, manager, grounds and plant growth facilities*
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Biometrics

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Genetic Resources Center

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BAO-RONG LU, *Ph D, germplasm specialist*
 JEAN-LOUIS PHAM, *Ph D, IRS seconded from ORSTOM*
 S. APPA RAO, *Ph D, project scientist*

Information Center

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 RAMIRO C. CABRERA, *BFA, manager, creative and production services, communication and publications services*
 CAROLYN DEDOLPH, *MS, science editor and writer*
 EUGENE P. HETTEL, *MA, senior science editor and writer*
 MARIO M. MOVILLON, *MS, manager, visitors, exhibition, and conference services*
 WALTER G. ROCKWOOD, *MS, consultant²*
 IAN M. WALLACE, *MLS, librarian*

International Programs Management Office

GLENN L. DENNING, *Ph D, scientist-international collaboration and head*
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 YOLANDA GARCIA, *Ph D, consultant³*
 JULIAN A. LAPITAN, *MS, senior associate scientist*
 WERNER W. STÜR, *Ph D, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical forage agronomist (IRRI affiliate scientist)*

Training Center

ROBERT T. RAAB, *Ph D, acting head*
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 DAVID MOWBRAY, *Ph D, consultant²*

¹Left during the year

²Joined and left during the year

³Joined during the year

⁴Cooperative research staff

⁵On project appointment

⁶Transferred from Entomology and Plant Pathology Division

Institutions collaborating with IRRI: partners making a difference

Australia

Australian Agency for International Development (AusAID)
Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR)
Australian National University (ANU)
Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO)
University of Melbourne
Yanco Agricultural Research Institute

Bangladesh

Bangladesh Agricultural Research Center (BARC)
Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI)
Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU)
Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI)
Ministry of Agriculture

Belgium

Belgian Agency for Development Cooperation (BADC)
Rijkuniversiteit Gent
Universite Catholique de Louvain

Bhutan

Ministry of Agriculture: Research, Extension, and Irrigation Division (REID)
National Resources Training Institute (NRTI)

Brazil

Centro Nacional de Pesquisa de Arroz e Feijão (CNPAP/EMBRAPA)

Brunei Darussalam

Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Industry and Primary Resources

Cambodia

Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF)

Canada

Canada Centre for Remote Sensing (CCRS)
Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA)
International Development Research Centre (IDRC)
McGill University
Universite Laval

China, People's Republic of

China National Rice Research Institute (CNNRI)
Chinese Academy of Agricultural Mechanization Sciences (CAAMS)
Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences (CAAS)
Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)
Fujian Academy of Agricultural Sciences (FAAS)
Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences (HAAS)
Ministry of Agriculture
Provincial Academies of Agricultural Sciences (e.g., Guangdong, Hunan, Fujian AAS)

South China Agricultural University
Southwest Agricultural University
University of Beijing
Zhejiang Agricultural University

Cuba

Cuban Rice Research Institute
State Committee for Economic Cooperation of the Republic of Cuba

Denmark

Danish International Development Agency (DANIDA)
Royal Veterinary and Agricultural University (RVAU)

Egypt

Agricultural Research and Training Center
Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation

France

Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement, département des cultures annuelles (CIRAD-CA)
Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS)
Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopération (ORSTOM)
Institut national de la recherche agronomique (INRA)

Germany

Deutsche Welthungerhilfe (DW)
Entwicklungspolitische Informationen (epi)
Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation (BMZ)
Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten, Forschung E.V. (FhG)
German Agency for Technical Cooperation (GTZ)
Justus Liebig-University of Giessen
Max-Planck Institute (MPI)
University of Goettingen
University of Hohenheim
University of Leipzig

India

Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University
Assam Agricultural University
Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI)
Directorate of Rice Research
G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology (GBPUAT)
The Government of India, Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine and Storage
Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI)
Indian Council for Agricultural Research (ICAR)
Indian Institute of Technology
Indira Gandhi Agricultural University

Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology
Punjab Agricultural University
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU)
University of Agricultural Sciences

Indonesia

Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (AARD)
Center for Agricultural Research Programming (CARP)
Central Research Institute for Food Crops (CRIFC)
Institut Pertanian Bogor (IPB)
Ministry of Agriculture
Universitas Gadjah Mada

Iran, Islamic Republic of

Agricultural and Natural Resources Research Organization of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
University of Guilan

Israel

Hebrew University of Jerusalem

Japan

Hokkaido University
Japan International Research Center for Agricultural Sciences (JIRCAS)
Mie University
National Agriculture Research Center (NARC)
Plantech Research Institute

Kazakhstan

Kazakh Academy of Agricultural Sciences
Kazakh Grain Research Institute

Kenya

Kenya Agricultural Research Institute (KARI)

Korea, Democratic People's Republic of

Rice Research Institute, Academy of Agricultural Sciences (AAS)

Korea, Republic of

Rural Development Administration (RDA)

Lao PDR

Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MAF)

Madagascar

Ministry of Research Applied to Development: National Center for Research Applied to Rural Development (FOFIFA)
University of Antananarivo

Malaysia

Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (MARDI)
Universiti Pertanian Malaysia

Mozambique

Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agronomica (INIA)
Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries
Sementes de Mocambique, Lda (SEMOC)

Myanmar

Ministry of Agriculture: Myanma Agriculture Service (MAS)

Nepal

Department of Agriculture: National Agricultural Research Centre (NARC)
Nepal Agricultural Research Council

Netherlands

C.T. de Wit Graduate School of Production Ecology (PE)
Information Center for Low External Input and Sustainable Agriculture (ILEIA)
Institute for Agrobiological and Soil Fertility Resource (AB-DLO)
Wageningen Agricultural University (WAU): Center for Agrobiological Research (CABO) and Theoretical Production Ecology (TPE)

Pakistan

National Agricultural Research Center (NARC)
Pakistan Agricultural Research Council (PARC)

Papua New Guinea

Department of Agriculture and Livestock
Trukai Industries Pty. Ltd.

Philippines

Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI)
Central Luzon State University (CLSU)
Department of Agriculture (DA)
Department of Science and Technology (DOST)
Los Baños Science Community (LBSC)
Mariano Marcos State University (MMSU)
National Irrigation Administration (NIA)
National Postharvest Institute for Research and Extension (NAPHIRE)
Philippine Council for Agriculture, Forestry, and Natural Resources Research and Development (PCARRD)
Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice)
University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB)
Visayas State College of Agriculture (VisCA)
Western Mindanao State University (WeMSU)

Sri Lanka

Department of Agriculture (DOASL)

Sweden

Swedish Agency for Research Cooperation with Developing Countries (SAREC)

Switzerland

CIBA-GEIGY Ltd.
Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC)
The Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH)

Taiwan, China

Ministry of Agriculture, Project Management Office

Tanzania

Ministry of Agriculture: Department of Research and Training

Thailand

Asian Institute of Technology
Chiang Mai University
Department of Agriculture
Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives
Kasetsart University
Pathumthani Rice Research Center
Population and Community Development Association (PDA)
Prachinburi Rice Research Center
Rice Research Institute

United Kingdom

Department for International Development (DFID)
Imperial College, University of London
Natural Resources Institute (NRI)
University of Birmingham
University of Nottingham
University of Oxford
University of Reading
University of Sheffield
University of Sussex

United States of America

Disney World
Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)
Ford Foundation, Inc. (FF)
Michigan State University
National Seed Storage Laboratory, Fort Collins
North Carolina State University (NCSU)
The Ohio State University
Oregon State University
Rockefeller Foundation (RF)
Soil Management Collaborative Research Support Program
Texas Agricultural and Mechanical University
University of Arkansas
University of California, Davis
University of Florida
University of Georgia
University of Hawaii: IBSNAT Project, NifTAL Project, and the Research Corporation (RCUH)
University of Maryland, College Park (UMCP)
United States Agency for International Development (USAID)
United States Department of Agriculture (USDA): Agricultural Research Service (ARS)
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Washington State University
Winrock International Institute for Agricultural Development

Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan Rice Research Institute

Vietnam

Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRRI)
Institute of Food Crops Research
Institute of Plant Protection
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD)
Ministry of Education and Training (MET)
University of Agriculture and Forestry (UAF)
University of Can Tho
Vietnam Agricultural Science Institute (VASI)

International Organizations

Asian Development Bank (ADB)
Asian Institute of Technology (AIT)
Asian Vegetable Research and Development Center (AVRDC)
Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International (CABI)
Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT)
Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo (CIMMYT)
Centro Internacional de la Papa (CIP)
Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)
International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD-World Bank)
International Centre for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA)
International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE)
International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management (ICLARM)
International Centre for Research in Agroforestry (ICRAF)
International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT)
International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC)
International Food Policy and Research Institute (IFPRI)
International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD)
International Institute of Rural Reconstruction (IIRR)
International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA)
International Irrigation Management Institute (IIMI)
International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI)
International Mycological Institute (IMI)
International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI)
International Service for National Agricultural Research (ISNAR)
Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA)
United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
UNDP: Global Resources Information Database Component (UNDP-GRID)
West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA)

Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR)

- CIAT** Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical
- CIFOR** Center for International Forestry Research
- CIMMYT** Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo
- CIP** Centro Internacional de la Papa
- ICARDA** International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas
- ICLARM** International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management
- ICRAF** International Centre for Research in Agroforestry
- ICRISAT** International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics
- IFPRI** International Food Policy Research Institute
- IIMI** International Irrigation Management Institute
- IITA** International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
- ILRI** International Livestock Research Institute
- IPGRI** International Plant Genetic Resources Institute
- IRRI** International Rice Research Institute
- ISNAR** International Service for National Agricultural Research
- WARDA** West Africa Rice Development Association

Mission of the CGIAR

Through its international research and related activities, to promote sustainable agriculture for food security in developing countries that enhance nutrition and well-being, especially of low-income people.

The CGIAR is an informal association of 53 public and private sector members from the South and North that provides more than US\$300 million annually to a global network (see map) of 16 international agricultural research centers, including IRRI. Established in 1971, the CGIAR envisions a world in which agricultural research has a positive impact on food security, income and employment generation, conservation of natural resources, and the environment.

CGIAR Centers have trained more than 50,000 agricultural scientists from developing countries over the past 25 years. Many of these scientists now form the nucleus of and provide leadership to national agricultural research systems (NARS) in their own countries.

Productivity and natural resources management are the twin pillars of CGIAR research on food crops, forestry, livestock, irrigation management, aquatic resources, and policy issues, and in its services to NARS. ■

How to contact IRRI offices

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IRRI's Mission Statement

Our goal

To improve the well-being of present and future generations of rice farmers and consumers, particularly those with low incomes.

Our objectives

To generate and disseminate rice-related knowledge and technology of short- and long-term environmental, social, and economic benefit and to help enhance national rice research systems.

Our strategy

We pursue our goal and objectives through

- interdisciplinary ecosystem-based programs in major rice environments
- scientific strength from discipline-based divisions
- anticipatory research initiatives
- exploring new scientific opportunities
- conservation and responsible use of natural resources
- sharing of germplasm, technologies, and knowledge
- participation of women in research and development
- partnership with farming communities, research institutions, and other organizations that share our goal

Our values

Our actions are guided by a commitment to

- excellence
- scientific integrity and accountability
- innovation and creativity
- diversity of opinion and approach
- teamwork and partnership
- service to clients
- cultural diversity
- gender consciousness
- indigenous knowledge
- environmental protection

The International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) was established in 1960 by the Ford and Rockefeller Foundations with the help and approval of the Government of the Philippines.

Today IRRI is one of 16 nonprofit international research centers supported by the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The CGIAR is sponsored by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank), and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). Its membership comprises donor countries, international and regional organizations, and private foundations.

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Cover photo Ram Cabrera

Printed in the Philippines

1997
ISBN 971-22-0097-3
International Rice Research Institute
P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines

